

Operationalisation of QUANTUM label data quality and utility framework

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Introduction

The Data Quality and Utility Label

The QUANTUM project has developed a standardised Data Quality and Utility Label to support transparency, comparability, and trust in datasets made available within the European Health Data Space (EHDS). The label translates the requirements of Article 78 of the EHDS Regulation into a structured and measurable framework, and enables data holders to assess and communicate the quality of their datasets in a consistent and comparable way.

The QUANTUM label is built around 12 data quality and utility dimensions that constitute the framework used to evaluate datasets. These dimensions are grouped into four EHDS categories: Access and Provision, Coverage, Data Documentation, and Technical Quality. The list of dimensions within each category is provided below (within parenthesis), and this document analyses each dimension following the same order.

- **Access and provision** (Accessibility)
- **Coverage** (Population coverage, Population representativity)
- **Data documentation** (Compliance, Data provenance, Metadata scope)
- **Technical quality** (Accuracy, Coherence, Completeness, Consistency, Precision, Validity)

Furthermore, the QUANTUM label also includes the evaluation of data holder maturity, which refers to the level of formalization and automation of data quality management processes at the organizational level. However, this component is out of scope for this document, which focuses on the assessment of dataset quality and utility, and will therefore not be addressed here.

Detailed specifications and supporting documentation are available on the main QUANTUM website at the following [link](#).

Scope of this document

To support data holders in the assessment of the quality and utility of their dataset, this document aims at providing further examples and guidelines on what each dimension represents and how to measure it. It is important to note that this document does not cover any possible scenario for each dimension, but provides some use cases to shed light on potential applications and ways to measure for the data holder. Furthermore, each data holder has a different way of measuring a dimension and different level of maturity, and hence automated processes. Therefore, it might happen that while reading a use case it might not resonate with your usual practices. These use cases are meant to provide examples and they are not the sole way to measure a specific dimension.

The content, structure, and methodological foundations of this framework are based on the specifications developed under the QUANTUM project.

To support this process, this document includes:

- **A data quality reporting template**, outlining the required dimensions and reporting elements.
- **Measurement guidelines**, offering concrete methodologies, implementation logic, best practices, and suggested metrics for each technical quality dimension.

This framework ensures efficiency and consistency across the data holders at evaluating the QUANTUM dimensions, and brings multiple benefits:

- It promotes consistent application of technical data quality methodologies.
- It improves comparability of datasets across institutions.
- It facilitates the assessment and reporting process for data holders.
- It strengthens transparency and auditability of reported quality levels.

This enables users to quickly understand and compare dataset quality in a structured and standardized manner.

The present document builds on preliminary work carried out by the Belgian Health Data Agency (HDA) in collaboration with the European Institute for Innovation through Health Data (i~HD). It was subsequently reviewed by QUANTUM partners to ensure alignment with QUANTUM directives and further enhanced to incorporate all the dimensions forming the aforementioned quality and utility framework.

This document precedes the implementation of the QUANTUM tool. Therefore, some terminology may differ from that used within the tool. To minimise ambiguity, most controls described in this document correspond directly to metrics as defined in the QUANTUM tool.

Structure of the document

This section describes the operational structure used to assess each dimension of the framework. It outlines how data quality objectives are translated into controls, implemented through dataset-level checks, and supported by explicit validation rules. In addition, it explains the distinction between critical and non-critical checks and provides guidance on how the framework should be applied in a transparent, reproducible, and traceable manner.

1. Dimensions

The dimensions listed below are the official ones, along with their definitions, as defined in the QUANTUM project. An additional table is then provided, presenting the same dimensions with simplified definitions and examples to facilitate understanding.

EHDS category	Dimension	Dimension definition
Access and provision	Accessibility	Accessibility refers to the dataset being accompanied by clear and transparent access and usage conditions
Coverage	Population coverage	Population coverage refers to the degree to which a dataset includes the potential eligible population
Coverage	Population representativity	Population representativity refers to the degree to which the data adequately represent the population in question
Data documentation	Compliance	Compliance refers to the degree to which data has attributes that adhere to ethical standards, conventions, protocols or regulations
Data documentation	Data provenance	Data provenance means a description of the source of the data, including context, purpose, method and technology of data generation, documenting agents involved in the provenance of data, data validation routines, source data verification, traceability of changes, and quality control of data
Data documentation	Metadata scope	Metadata scope refers to the availability, comprehensiveness, level of detail of metadata and data dictionary that help users understand the data being used
Technical quality	Accuracy	Accuracy refers to the degree to which observations correctly describe what it was designed to measure
Technical quality	Coherence	Coherence is defined as the dimension that expresses how different parts of the dataset are uniform in their representation and meaning over time, such as formats, semantics (stability of the data models), and methods

EHDS category	Dimension	Dimension definition
Technical quality	Completeness	Completeness refers to the degree to which all information that could be available is present in a particular dataset
Technical quality	Consistency	Consistency refers to the degree to which data has attributes that are plausible and are uniform with other data and over time
Technical quality	Precision	Precision refers to the degree of approximation by which data can represent reality
Technical quality	Validity	Validity refers to the degree to which representations of data in a dataset conform to the specification of a data model or data models

Dimension	Explanation	Example
Accessibility	Does the dataset description clearly state how to access the data? How long does it approximately take to get access to it?	The dataset that is applied for secondary use under EHDS regulation is marked as “non-public” in the Access rights field of the catalogue description. A score of 0 is assigned if the average time to access the data after a complete application exceeds six months.
Population Coverage	Does the dataset include all members or units of the target population that should theoretically be captured for the intended purpose?	If a national health survey aims to assess healthcare access across a country but only collects data from urban hospitals, rural populations are excluded from the coverage, creating gaps in the overall assessment.
Population Representativity	Does the dataset adequately reflect the characteristics of the target population relevant to its intended use?	If a dataset used to analyse elderly care outcomes contains mostly patients aged 18-44, older age groups are under-represented, limiting the validity of conclusions for the elderly population.
Compliance	Is the dataset collected, processed, stored, and shared in accordance with applicable legal, regulatory, ethical, and technical standards.	A dataset includes documented GDPR compliance, a clearly defined legal basis for processing, and evidence of ethics committee approval.

Data Provenance	Can the user understand where the data come from, how they were generated or collected, and what main processing steps were applied before the dataset reached its current form?	A dataset is accompanied by documentation stating that the clinical records were extracted from a hospital information system, the images were generated from tissue samples scanned in a pathology laboratory, and both sub-datasets were later cleaned, linked, pseudonymised, and integrated by a university before release for secondary use.
Metadata Scope	Is there sufficient context provided for dataset interpretation, and is the additional information provided using standardised vocabularies to facilitate comparability and interoperability?	If a dataset is missing context, e.g. measurement units, coded value options, collection timeframe - or if such information is provided in a non-standardised manner - it creates an usability issue: the dataset might become unusable or not suitable for e.g. reviewing current trends.
Completeness	Is all information that could be available present?	Every patient record should have a blood type recorded. If 15% of records are blank, that is a completeness issue.
Consistency	Do the values match across systems and time for the same entity?	If the EHR says a patient's blood type is "O+", the lab system should also say "O+" for that patient, both today and next year.
Accuracy	Does the recorded value reflect the true real-world value?	The record says blood type is "O+", but lab test confirms "A+". ¹
Coherence	Does the dataset remain comparable over time and across sources, with the same concepts represented consistently (formats, codes, units, methods) and any changes in data patterns documented and justified?	If blood type is coded using {O+, O-, A+, A-, B+, B-, AB+, AB-}, that code list should not change to free-text ("O positive") without a documented, controlled process.

¹ While the formal QUANTUM definition of Accuracy may be interpreted at the individual level, the underlying measurement definitions developed during the study primarily address accuracy at the variable or sample level—i.e. ensuring that the statistical distribution of the data reflects what it is intended to represent, rather than focusing on individual records. The example provided remains valid; however, validation at the individual level is often challenging. For instance, the example could alternatively be interpreted as a consistency issue between two data sources, even if one (e.g. a laboratory test) is considered the ground truth.

Validity	Do the values conform to the allowed rules or domains?	Blood type must be one of {O+, O-, A+, A-, B+, B-, AB+, AB-}. An entry like “OP” is invalid.
Precision	Is the level of detail sufficient to represent reality?	Recording “O” without the Rh factor (+/-) is too imprecise for clinical use.

2. Controls

Within each dimension, we define one or more controls. A control represents a specific technical quality objective within a dimension. For example, the completeness dimension may include controls such as:

- Mandatory field completeness
- Conditional completeness
- Cross-dataset completeness

3. Checks

A check is the concrete, dataset-level execution of a control. It operationalizes a defined quality objective by verifying whether the dataset complies with specific expectations and produces a measurable outcome (e.g., percentage of missing values, rate of valid codes, or number of records with references to non-existent or invalid entries in related datasets). While a control defines which aspect of quality is being assessed, a check defines how that assessment is performed for a particular dataset.

A single control can generate multiple checks, depending on the number of relevant variables, relationships, or validation rules involved. For example, under the Mandatory Field Completeness control, separate checks may be defined for:

- Completeness of Patient ID
- Completeness of Date of Birth
- Completeness of Diagnosis.

Each of these represents an individual measurement, yet all fall under the same completeness control. The number, scope, and configuration of checks will vary depending on:

- Dataset structure (e.g., available fields, relational dependencies, system architecture)
- Operational context or intended use (e.g., clinical operations, reporting, research extraction)
- Applicable business or regulatory rules (e.g., legal requirements, coding standards, institutional policies)

All checks must be clearly documented, reproducible, and traceable to their underlying control and associated business rules.

4. Rules

Each check is grounded in one or more rules. A rule is a formally defined validation condition that specifies what is expected in the data in order to meet a given technical quality objective. Rules translate technical data quality requirements into verifiable statements that can be tested against the dataset. They may be expressed:

- In natural language (for documentation and governance purposes), and/or
- In executable form within validation scripts, SQL queries, rule engines, or data quality tools

Examples of rules include:

- "Patient ID must not be empty"
- "ICD-10 codes must correspond to the official classification"
- "Date of birth must be earlier than the current date"

These rules are defined by business stakeholders, data owners, or regulators based on the intended use of the data.

5. Critical vs non-critical checks

To support structured interpretation, prioritization, and governance, each check is assigned a critical level.

- Critical checks are essential for data technical usability, legal compliance, or operational integrity. Failure of a critical check may render the dataset, or a specific use case, unsuitable for this intended purpose until adequately documented or addressed.
- Non-critical checks provide important quality insights but are not essential. Their failure may reduce confidence or signal areas for improvement but does not automatically block technical usability.

Criticality is assigned at the check level, not at the dimension or field level. The same field may be involved in both critical and non-critical checks depending on the validation rule and context. Critical classifications must be documented and auditable.

Note: Criticality may vary by domain, system, or dataset purpose. While we propose default classifications, organizations are encouraged to define and document criticality based on their specific use cases.

6. Application of the framework

For each technical quality dimension, this document provides practical guidance and structured scenarios to support implementation. These serve as a decision framework to help data holders determine which controls, checks, and rules are applicable to their dataset.

Checks may be:

- Fully automated (e.g., scripted validation queries)
- Semi-automated (e.g., tool-assisted review)
- Manual (e.g., documented procedural verification)

Provided that the methodology is:

- Clearly documented
- Reproducible
- Traceable to defined rules and controls
- Consistently applied across reporting cycles

This ensures that technical data quality assessments remain transparent and auditable across data holders.

Access and Provision Dimensions

1. Accessibility

1.1. Definition

QUANTUM defines accessibility as the “dataset being accompanied by clear and transparent access and usage conditions”.

In practice, accessibility assesses the availability and usability of data for data users for secondary purposes and whether there are policies available which clearly outline the roles of health data holders and data users with regard to access to and availability of the data.

The first metric, availability of a data access and usage policy, refers to the dataset description in the national or EU level health dataset catalogue being clear and up to date, with information provided to the potential data user about the access and usage policy of the data. The recommended measurement

approach, defined by QUANTUM, is to provide the information in the DCAT Access rights property as part of the dataset description based on HealthDCAT-AP metadata specification. It is also recommended to provide all possible additional information in other relevant metadata fields of the dataset description, and to add links to necessary additional sources of information. This is especially necessary if there are multiple ways to access the data. Health data holders should consider if data is openly and clearly available to data users in a form that facilitates accurate interpretation and meaningful comparison. Data users should be able to access data without unnecessary barriers.

The second metric, average time from data access application to data release, refers to the average time for an external data user to get access to the data after the health data holder has received the complete application. The recommended measurement approach, defined by QUANTUM, is to provide the average time using digital time-stamps for the process. The measurement should only cover the period from the data holder's receipt of the application to the actual data access or release date. It must not include the initial application processing time handled by the health data access body.

The response chosen should be based on information gained from practical experience, if available. It is known that the access time is not only dependent on the health data holder and their processes. It might also be related, for example, to how well the application was completed, if the applicant understood what data are available and if the data meets their requirements. However, there is a lot that the health data holder can do to help, including providing detailed and up-to-date metadata. While the average time for access might not be an intrinsic quality dimension of the data itself, access time can be a critical factor in the decision to use a dataset for a potential data user.

1.2. List of accessibility controls

Metric 1: Reviewing the availability of a data access and usage policy

This control evaluates whether the dataset is accompanied by comprehensive documentation on how data users can access the dataset. It is scored on an ordinal scale of 0-2 reflecting increasing levels of documentation of policies and procedures regarding accessing the dataset.

Applied to case: we assess the fictional dataset against the three ordinal levels considering the documentation available.

What to check: Is the dataset accompanied by documentation clearly describing where and how to apply for access to the dataset? Is there information available on who can be contacted in relation to questions or queries on how to access the dataset?

Metric 2: Calculating the average time for an external user to get access to the data after the health data holder has received the application based on time-stamps or other available information

This control evaluates the average time from data access application to release date of the data. It is scored on an ordinal scale 0-3, reflecting decreasing levels of time from access to release of a dataset.

Applied to case: we assess the fictional national registry dataset against the four ordinal levels considering the time from data access application to data release in terms of months outlined.

What to check: the average time in months from a complete data access application by the data user to data release by the data holder. The measurement should only cover the period from the data holder's receipt of the completed application to the actual data access or release and should not reflect any time that is taken in the initial application processing by the Health Data Access Body.

1.3. How to apply the accessibility checks

Metric #1 Availability of a data access & usage policy

Score	Label	Definition	Applied example
0	No policy available	No documentation exists in the published metadata describing how the data can be applied for secondary use.	The dataset has no accompanying usage policy describing how and where the dataset can be accessed and the associated procedures to access the data are absent.
1	Basic policy available	Documentation exists in the published metadata describing how the data can be applied for secondary use. In the basic level the HealthDCAT-AP properties Access rights (options: NON_PUBLIC, PUBLIC, RESTRICTED), Applicable legislation, Contact point and Health data access body must have information filled in at the dataset level. The HealthDCAT-AP specification related instructions and guidelines must be followed regarding how to fill in the information.	The dataset description includes some basic information on where the data may be accessed but no clear policy is available describing how a data user can apply for access to the data and under what conditions the data may be made available.

2	Comprehensive policy available	<p>Documentation exists in the published metadata describing how the data can be applied for secondary use comprehensively. In addition to the Access rights, Applicable legislation, Contact point and Health data access body properties, links to additional information and any other needed information is provided for the user to understand comprehensively, which ways and procedures there are for applying the data for secondary use. The HealthDCAT-AP specification related instructions and guidelines must be followed regarding how to fill in the information.</p> <p>If there are several ways to get access to the data for secondary use, it is clearly stated in the metadata description and up-to-date contact information is provided, where additional information can be requested if necessary.</p>	The dataset is accompanied by a comprehensive, clear and available policy outlining how and where access to the data can be applied for outlining the roles and responsibilities of the data holder and data user. There is also additional information on who to contact in the case of questions or queries regarding applying for access to the data.
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Availability of a data and usage policy is recorded as a single ordinal score (0-2).

Metric #2 Average time from data access application to data release

Score	Label	Definition	Applied example
0	More than 6 months	The average time from data access application to data release for a specific dataset is more than 6 months.	The data user submits a fully completed data access application to a national registry. From the time the registry receives the fully completed access application to the time of the release of the data to the user is more than 6 months.
1	3 to 6 months	The average time from data access application to data release for a specific dataset is 3 to 6 months.	The data user submits a fully completed data access application to a national registry. From the time the registry receives the fully completed access application to the time of the release of the data to the user is 3 to 6 months.
2	1 to 3 months	The average time from data access application to data release for a specific dataset is 1 to 3 months.	The data user submits a fully completed data access application to a national registry. From the time the registry receives the fully completed access application to the time of the release of the data to the user is 1 to 3 months.

3	Less than 1 month	The average time from data access application to data release for a specific dataset is less than one month.	The data user submits a fully completed data access application to a national registry. From the time the registry receives the fully completed access application to the time of the release of the data to the user is less than 1 month.
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Average time is recorded as a single ordinal score (0-3).

Coverage Dimensions

1. Population Coverage

1.1. Definition

QUANTUM defines the population coverage dimension as the “the degree to which a dataset includes the potential eligible population” (e.g., clinical, demographic, geographic, administrative criteria...).

In practice, population coverage refers to the extent to which all individuals who meet the eligibility criteria are actually in the dataset. It assesses whether the dataset sufficiently reflects the size of the target population, independent of how well the characteristics of that population are distributed within it. Population coverage is concerned with the extent to which the target population is represented, in terms of inclusion and completeness. In practice, full population coverage is often not feasible due to constraints such as cost or analytical complexity. Therefore, coverage metrics must be interpreted in context, and a low sampled-to-target population ratio does not necessarily imply inadequate coverage. A dataset may have high representativity (i.e. well-balanced characteristics) but low coverage (i.e. only a small fraction of the eligible population is included), or conversely high coverage but poor representativity if certain subgroups are disproportionately captured.

As such, population coverage and population representativity are complementary dimensions:

- Coverage answers: *How much of the eligible population is included?*
- Representativity answers: *How well does the included population reflect the target population?*

Both dimensions must be interpreted jointly to assess the fitness-for-use of a dataset for population-level analyses.

1.2. List of Population Coverage controls

Based on the definition above, we distinguish one main control for population coverage, assessed through a quantitative measurement approach.

1. Coverage rate control

This control evaluates the proportion of the eligible population that is included in the dataset. It provides a quantitative estimate of dataset exhaustiveness relative to a clearly defined reference population. Population coverage is a proportion-based concept, unlike representativity which depends on distributional comparisons. A percentage-based measure is therefore appropriate to quantify the degree of inclusion.

What to check:

Is the dataset accompanied by sufficient information to determine:

- The definition of the eligible (reference) population
- The number of individuals included in the dataset
- The proportion of the eligible population captured

Coverage can be measured as a ratio between observed and eligible population. The result is expressed as a percentage and interpreted using standardised thresholds aligned with the QUANTUM specification.

Coverage rate	Interpretation
< 80%	Limited coverage
80% - < 90%	Good coverage
90% - < 95%	Very good coverage
95% - 100%	Perfect coverage

Example:

A human biomonitoring study aims to estimate PFAS exposure in the adult population of *Region X* (containing 2 million individuals). Due to the high cost and complexity of laboratory analyses, a representative sample of 1000 individuals is collected. The population coverage rate is therefore $1000/20000000000 = 0.05\%$.

Although numerically very low, this coverage is considered appropriate, as the study is designed for statistical inference rather than full population enumeration. This illustrates that population coverage must be interpreted in light of study design and feasibility constraints.

1.3. How to apply the Population Coverage checks

Population coverage must always be assessed relative to a clearly defined reference population. Without this reference, coverage cannot be meaningfully interpreted.

Key considerations:

- Definition of the reference population

The eligible population must be explicitly defined (e.g. patient within a healthcare system, inclusion/exclusion criteria, context of data capture...). Differences in scope directly affect coverage interpretation.

- Data source limitations

Coverage may be constrained by structural factors such as healthcare system boundaries, reporting obligations, geographic or institutional scope.

- Relationship with representativity

High coverage does not guarantee representativity. For example a dataset covering 95% of a population may still under-represent specific subgroups (e.g. rural populations). Or a dataset with 60% coverage may still be representative if sampling is well-designed and documented. Therefore, coverage results must always be interpreted alongside the population representativity score.

- Use case dependency

The importance of coverage varies depending on the intended use. High coverage is critical for epidemiological studies and health system monitoring. Moderate or even low population coverage may be acceptable depending on representative sampling (e.g., human biomonitoring) can yield meaningful and policy-relevant results despite limited coverage.

2. Population Representativity

2.1. Definition

QUANTUM defines the population representativity dimension as “the degree to which the data adequately represent the population in question”.

In practice, population representativity assesses whether the individuals captured in a dataset are fair and unbiased reflection of the real-world population relevant to the dataset’s intended use, either primary or secondary. A dataset may be technically complete, valid, and accurate, yet it might still produce misleading or ungeneralisable results of the underlying population is systematically skewed. For example, by over- or under-representing certain age groups, ethnicities, or sociodemographic backgrounds.

Representativity is not an absolute property. It is always evaluated relative to a reference population and relative to an intended use. A dataset drawn exclusively from a tertiary hospital may be perfectly representative for studies of complex inpatient care, yet poorly representative for primary care research. This fit-for-purpose nature means that representativity must be assessed in context, with a clearly stated reference population and analytical purpose.

2.2. List of Population Representativity controls

Based on the definition above, we distinguish one main control for population representativity, assessed through a structured ordinal scoring approach. To illustrate how the control operates, we use a consistent example throughout a dataset from a fictional regional healthcare system. The dataset intended for use in a study on diabetes prevalence across the general audit population.

Table 1: Dataset population summary

Patient ID	Age group	Ethnicity	Socioeconomic group	Primary diagnosis
300000001	65-74	Group A	Low	Diabeter type 2
300000002	45-54	Group B	Middle	Diabeter type 2
300000003	18-44	Group A	High	Hypertension
300000004	55-64	Group C	Middle	Diabeter type 2
300000005	75 +	Group A	Low	Heart failure
300000006	18-44	Group B	High	Diabeter type 2

1. Sampling representativity control

This control evaluates whether the dataset is accompanied by sufficient documentation about how its population was selected or assembled. It is scored on an ordinal scale of 0 to 3, reflecting increasing levels of evidence and coverage.

The rationale for an ordinal rather than a percentage-based score is that representativity cannot be meaningfully quantified without first establishing that appropriate sampling documentation exists. The scale therefore captures both the presence and the quality of that evidence, as well as the ultimate case where sampling is no longer a concern because the full target population is covered.

Applied to case: We assess the fictional diabetes prevalence dataset against the four ordinal levels, considering both the documentation available and the known coverage of the dataset relative to the national adult diabetic population.

What to check: Is the dataset accompanied by sampling documentation, and does that documentation demonstrate that the sample reflects the reference population across key characteristics to the intended use (e.g., age group, ethnicity, socioeconomic background)?

Ways to measure:

Score	Label	Definition	Applied example
0	No sampling information	No documentation exists describing how the dataset's population was selected or assembled. Representativity cannot be assessed.	The diabetes dataset has no accompanying methodology document. It is unclear how patients were selected or whether any population was targeted.
1	Sampling information does not demonstrate representativity	Documentation exists describing the sampling approach, but the evidence provided is insufficient to confirm that the sample reflects the reference population. Documentation may be incomplete, or known gaps are unaddressed.	The dataset includes a brief note stating it was drawn from two urban hospitals, but provides no comparison against national age, ethnicity, or socioeconomic distributions. Urban over-representation is unaddressed.
2	Sampling information demonstrates representativity	Documentation exists and provides sufficient evidence, through comparison against a reference population, stratified sampling records, or equivalent that the sample reflects the reference population across key characteristics relevant to the intended use.	The dataset is accompanied by a sampling report comparing its age group, ethnicity, and socioeconomic distributions against national health survey benchmarks, showing deviations within acceptable margins and explaining residual gaps.
3	Dataset contains all expected population	The dataset is not a sample. It captures all members of the target population within the defined scope (e.g., a national registry with complete enrolment, or an exhaustive administrative extract). Sampling representativity is not applicable because no selection process was applied.	The dataset is a complete national extract of all adults diagnosed with diabetes in the reference period, drawn from a mandatory reporting system with no exclusion criteria.

Note: A score of 3 does not imply that the dataset is free of all representativity concerns. For example, a complete registry may still exclude individuals who were never diagnosed or never entered the health system. Data holders achieving a score of 3 are encouraged to document any such structural limitations alongside their score.

2.3. How to apply the Population Representativity checks

Unlike the technical dimensions, a low representativity score does not mean the data are wrong, it means their scope is limited or insufficiently documented. Criticality is therefore always context-dependent: the same dataset may have a critical representativity requirement for a population-level epidemiological study, but only a non-critical one for a clinical safety signal analysis where the question concerns a mechanism rather than a prevalence estimate. The primary function of this dimension is transparency, ensuring that users understand the population from which data were drawn and can apply appropriate caution, weighting or, caveats in their analyses.

Overview of the scenarios:

Scenario	Dataset type	Sampling documentation available?	Reference population defined?	Likely score	Checks to apply
0	Any	No	No	0	Document absence. Score = 0
1	Sample dataset	Yes, partial	No	1	Sampling representativity check. Score = 1
2	Sample dataset	Yes, full	Yes	2	Sampling representativity check. Score = 2
3	Complete registry / exhaustive extract	Not applicable	Yes	3	Confirm completeness Score = 3; document structural exclusions
4	Sample dataset	Yes, full	Partially available	1-2	Apply check within available reference scope. Flag missing strata and score accordingly.

Population representativity is reported as a single ordinal score (0-3) accompanied by a written justification. The justification should include the reference population used for assessment, the key characteristics examined, the nature of any identified gaps or deviations, and whether any deviations are by design and have been annotated as such. To contextualise the

Data Documentation Dimensions

1. Compliance

1.1. Definition

QUANTUM defines the compliance dimensions as the degree to which data has attributes that adhere to ethical standards, conventions, protocols, or regulations.

In practice, compliance refers to the extent to which a dataset is collected, processed, stored, and made available in accordance with applicable legal, regulatory, ethical, and organisational requirements. This includes adherence to data protection regulations (e.g., GDPR), ethical approvals, infrastructure requirements, data governance policies, and domain-specific standards (e.g., clinical coding conventions, research protocols).

Compliance ensures that data is not only technically usable but also legally and ethically permissible for its intended use. A dataset may be complete and accurate, yet usability may be diminished by a lack of sufficient compliance.

1.2. List of Compliance controls

Based on the definition above, we distinguish three main types of compliance controls:

1. Regulatory and legal compliance control

This control evaluates whether the dataset complies with applicable legal and regulatory frameworks governing data collection, processing, storage, and sharing.

What to check:

- Is there documented compliance with relevant regulations? Specifically, are there sufficient protections for personal data to meet GDPR requirements? Is it available and well documented enough to comply with EHDS demands?
- Are legal bases for data processing defined? For example, data for research as a secondary use of research must pass an evaluation by the appropriate ethics board.

- Are there sufficient technical measures taken at the infrastructure level to ensure the proper implementation of data protection measures? For example, are the data correctly anonymized/pseudoanonymized and is the processing environment secured from cyberattacks?

Ways to measure:

Score	Label	Definition
0	No compliance evidence	No documentation demonstrating compliance with applicable regulations
1	Partial compliance documented	Some regulatory aspects documented, but gaps exist (e.g., unclear legal basis, incomplete safeguards)
2	Full compliance documented	Clear, complete documentation demonstrating compliance with all applicable legal and regulatory requirements

2. Ethical compliance control

This control evaluates whether the dataset complies with ethical standards governing the use of data, particularly in relation to human subjects.

What to check:

- Has the dataset received approval from an ethics committee or institutional review board, where applicable?
- Is informed consent obtained and documented, or is a valid exemption justified?
- Are there safeguards protecting vulnerable populations?
- Are ethical use constraints documented?
- Are measures taken to ensure that the use of the data does not perpetuate discrimination, bias, or unfairly disadvantage specific communities?
- Have the users learned and confirmed their understanding of the permitted use cases as well as their responsibility in protecting and correctly treating the data?

Ways to measure:

Score	Label	Definition
0	No ethical documentation	No evidence of ethical approval or consent framework
1	Partial ethical compliance	Ethical considerations documented but incomplete (e.g., missing consent details or unclear approval)

		scope)
2	Full ethical compliance	Comprehensive documentation of ethical approval, consent procedures, and safeguards

3. Standards and protocol adherence control

This control evaluates whether the dataset adheres to recognised standards, conventions, and protocols relevant to its domain.

What to check:

- Do the processing tools, services, and environments meet national and international standards for quality?
- Are the relevant protocols from the International Standards Organization followed? Depending on the use case, it could be ISO 27001, 9001, or others.
- Do the processing tools have CE markings and have they passed through MDR certification where necessary?
- Are standard coding systems used (e.g., ICD, SNOMED, ATC)?
- Are data formats and structures aligned with recognised standards (e.g., HL7, FHIR)?
- Are data collection and processing protocols documented and followed?
- Are deviations from standards justified and documented?

Ways to measure

Score	Label	Definition
0	No standard adherence	No use of recognised standards or protocols
1	Partial adherence	Some standards applied, but inconsistently or incomplete
2	Full adherence	Dataset consistently follows recognised standards and protocols, with documentation

1.3. How to apply the Compliance checks

Compliance checks should be applied as a combination of document review, process verification, and metadata validation. Each control is evaluated independently and assigned an ordinal score.

Example scenario:

Scenario	Description	Likely outcome
0	No legal, ethical, or standards documentation available	All controls score 0
1	GDPR compliance stated but no ethical approval or standardisation evidence	Mixed scores (e.g., legal = 1, ethical = 0, standards = 1)
2	Full GDPR documentation, ethics approval, and use of ICD/HL7 Standards	All controls score 2

2. Data Provenance

Before reading the current section, it is important to remind the reader that the purpose of this document is to support data holders in assessing the quality and utility of the dataset under evaluation and in reporting the results within the QUANTUM labelling tool. Therefore, the assessment criteria described below should not be interpreted as binding procedures formally imposed by the QUANTUM project. Rather, they represent an ideal assessment scenario in which the data holder has an adequate level of maturity and the necessary processes already in place. Therefore provenance documentation may be implemented at different levels of technical maturity. While machine-readable, standardised representations (e.g., CPM/PROV-compliant) are encouraged as best practice, less formal approaches such as structured or narrative documentation may constitute an acceptable minimum, provided that provenance remains

transparent, auditable, and sufficient to support fitness-for-purpose assessment.

2.1. Definition

QUANTUM defines the Data Provenance dimension as "a description of the source of the data, including context, purpose, method and technology of data generation, documenting agents involved in the provenance of data, data validation routines, source data verification, traceability of changes, and quality control of data".

In practice, data provenance refers to the documented history of a dataset, describing where the data originate; how they were generated, processed and transformed; by whom, and under which technical and organizational conditions. It allows data users to understand the pathway from the dataset to its origin and to support its quality assessment, which would take into account the main steps that may have influenced the data semantics, content, or structure.

These steps can occur at any point along the chain from the origin to the assessed dataset. For biological-material pipelines, they can include acquisition, transport, storage, and processing of precursors. For data generation, they include the generation procedure itself and the conditions under which it was performed. For post-generation processing, they can include extraction, transfer, linkage, cleaning, pseudonymisation, validation, quality control, aggregation, and any other operation carried out before the dataset was released or reused. Each such step can influence the semantics, content, or structure of the assessed data, and provenance documentation is the means by which these influences are made traceable.

Without sufficient provenance documentation, it is difficult to determine whether a dataset is suitable for a given purpose, i.e., whether important transformation steps have taken place, what technology and systems were used, whether quality controls were applied, what were the responsible actors, or whether changes across versions can be explained — even if the dataset appears complete, valid, or accurate on its own terms.

This chain of evidence supports the assessment of both the source and the reliability of the processes through which the data were produced and maintained. Since the fitness-for-purpose of a dataset is directly affected by the conditions under which its source was acquired and processed, this link to the source and precursors of the source cannot be omitted from a complete provenance record.

Running example

The following use case is serving as a running example to explain provenance-related concepts throughout this dimension.

The use case concerns the quality assessment of an integrated health dataset composed of two sub-datasets originating from the same donor. The first sub-dataset contains clinical records entered manually by a doctor into the Hospital Information System (HIS) of Hospital A; these records are subsequently extracted from the HIS and cleaned at a University. The second sub-dataset is an image dataset (or its subset) derived from a tissue sample. The tissue sample is acquired from the donor at Hospital B, transferred to a Pathology lab, where it is processed — including cutting into slices and additional preparation steps such as staining or fixing — producing one or more slides. A slide is then scanned at the Pathology lab, producing raw image data, which is subsequently annotated at the same Pathology lab. The clinical sub-dataset and the annotated image sub-dataset are transferred to the University, where they are integrated and pre-processed into the assessed dataset. The assessed dataset is to be used in a Data usage step, which may be an analysis or the training of an AI model. The pipeline is multi-organizational: objects are passed between Hospital A, Hospital B, the Pathology lab, and the University, and each organization can provide provenance only about the part of the life cycle it carries out. The structure of the use case is depicted in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Running example for the Data Provenance dimension.

The following terms are used throughout this section. Application of the definitions to the example is depicted in Figure 2.2.

- **Precursor** is a sample or a derived sample².
 - E.g., a raw human-derived sample (e.g., blood, saliva, tissue biopsies, ...) or a sample at various processing steps (e.g., FFPE, DNA extracts, ...).
 - *Application to the running example:* The precursors are, for the imaging sub-dataset, the acquired tissue sample and each derived sample produced by processing (cut slices and

² Also referred to as a primary sample or a processed sample.

further-prepared slides) prior to the one used as source. The clinical sub-dataset has no precursor.

- **Source** is a physical object (e.g., sample/derived sample/human) from which data is generated or observed.
 - *Application to the running example:* The source is, for the imaging sub-dataset, the slide that is scanned. The clinical sub-dataset has no physical source; the clinical records are themselves source data, generated by manual data entry.
- **Source data** refers to the raw data produced by a data generation procedure, which may be applied to the source.
 - *Application to the running example:* The source data are, for the imaging sub-dataset, the raw image data produced by scanning the slide; for the clinical sub-dataset, the clinical records as entered into the HIS.
- **Assessed data** refers to the dataset being assessed.
 - Assessed data may be a subset of source data. Any data, including source data, may be assessed data.
 - *Application to the running example:* The assessed data are the integrated, pre-processed dataset produced by the University from the annotated clinical and annotated image sub-datasets. The example illustrates how the provenance controls apply to an integrated, multi-source assessed dataset.
- **Origin** is the entity from which the first precursor, the source, or — in the absence of both — the assessed data itself was obtained.
 - For biological-material pipelines, origin is typically the patient or donor who provided the precursor or source. For data generated without an underlying physical object (e.g., clinical data entered manually into an information system), origin is the data subject to whom the data pertains, if any, or the agent authoring the data otherwise.
 - *Application to the running example:* The origin is the donor, from whom the tissue sample is acquired and to whom the clinical records pertain. The running example has a single origin for both sub-datasets.

As a result, the resulting pipeline is formed as³: origin → (precursor → ... → precursor →)? (source →)? source data → data → data →

³ Parenthesised segments are present only when the corresponding applicability branch from *Pipeline stage-specific provenance types* applies.

Figure 2.2: Definitions applied to the running example.

Pipeline stage-specific provenance types

Data provenance can be understood as comprising three complementary aspects that together cover the entire chain. **Data precursors provenance** describes processes applied to the source and its precursors prior to data generation. This includes, for instance, documentation of biological material acquisition or processing steps, prior the material was used for data generation. **Data generation provenance** describes the data generation process, i.e., the source and the conditions under which source data was generated. **Data derivation provenance** describes how data was obtained from source data, including any changes applied. Together, these aspects enable complete traceability from the data in its current form to its origins. The concepts are depicted in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Pipeline stage-specific types of provenance information.

The three provenance types are **complementary, not disjoint**. A single real-world object or step may fall within more than one definition. For example, a biological sample acting as the *source* of data generation may also have a prior life-cycle of acquisition, transport, and processing — that prior life-cycle is described under *data precursors provenance*, while the generation step in which the sample was used is described under *data generation provenance*.

Each of the three provenance types is applicable only under specific conditions, **determined by the nature of the assessed data**:

- *Data precursors provenance* is applicable when the assessed data, directly or via predecessors, was generated from biological material. It has no applicable content when no biological precursor exists in the pipeline.
- *Data generation provenance* is applicable when the assessed data is either source data or was derived from source data produced by a data generation procedure applied to a source.
- *Data derivation provenance* is applicable when the assessed data was obtained from source data or from data derived from source data. It has no applicable content when the assessed data is the same as the source data, i.e., no processing or transformation was applied after data generation.

Determining which types are applicable is itself part of the Data Provenance dimension assessment: the applicability branches taken for a given assessed dataset shall be implicit or explicitly documented so that a user can reconstruct the pipeline shape.

The following sections explicitly lists items, which are to be covered by each type of provenance. The same item may recur across types with per-activity values. For example, a *responsible organization identifier* documents the organization accountable for the specific activity being described — a precursor handling event under *data precursors provenance*, the generation step under *data generation provenance*, and a derivation step under *data derivation provenance* — and may therefore appear in each type with a different value. The same applies to identifiers, timestamps, and method references attached to activity-specific bullets.

Data precursors provenance

Data precursors provenance means a description of acquisition and handling of precursors of the source, which are primarily biological samples.

In particular, data precursors provenance is expected to cover:

- Patient/donor identifier(s):** If applicable, and if permitted under applicable privacy and consent rules, a privacy-preserving pseudonymized identifier(s) of patient(s) or donor(s) which provided biological material.
- Precursor (sample) identifier(s):** If applicable, and if permitted under applicable privacy and consent rules, identifier(s) of all precursors of the source and their mutual relations.
- Precursor(s) (sample(s)) handling:** A description of all significant events that may affect the quality of the precursors, source datasets, or derived datasets, covering:
 - Type: sample acquisition, sample transport, relabelling, long-term storage of sample, sample retrieval from the storage, any kind of samples processing, sample receipt, sample distribution.

- If applicable, for each event, the method (e.g., a link to an SOP),
- Related timestamps;
- Responsible organization(s) identifier(s):** Identifier(s) of all organizations that were involved in precursor(s) handling.

Data generation provenance

Data generation provenance means a description of how source data was generated prior to any subsequent processing or transformation. In particular, data generation provenance is expected to cover:

- Source identifier:** If applicable, and if permitted under applicable privacy and consent rules, a privacy-preserving pseudonymized identifier(s) of the source(s) from which the source data was generated.
- Source organization identifier:** If applicable, identifier(s) of the organization(s) that provided a particular source.
- Data generation step:** A description of the data generation process, covering:
 - Type (e.g., sequencing, scanning),
 - Method (e.g., a link to an SOP),
 - technology used (e.g., a device (manufacturer + serial number) or software (software provider, software name, version)).
- Responsible organization identifier:** An identifier of the organization that performed the data generation.
- Generated dataset identifier:** Identifier of the dataset that was generated by the data generation step.

Data derivation provenance

Data derivation provenance means a description of how assessed data was obtained from the source data or from data derived from the source data. In this case, the provenance information is expected to cover:

- Preceding dataset(s) identifier(s):** If applicable, and if permitted, a privacy-preserving pseudonymized identifier(s) of dataset(s) from which the assessed data is derived (e.g., source data).
- Data processing step:** A description of all significant events that may affect the quality of the assessed data, covering:
 - The type of operation applied and any changes made.
 - In case of automated data processing, a reference to the tool used for the data processing and used configuration.

- Responsible organization identifier:** Identifier(s) of all organizations that were involved in the data derivation.

Relationship to provenance standards

Provenance information may be documented in various forms, from natural language descriptions to structured metadata or machine-readable representations. The degree to which documentation follows a recognized standard directly affects its utility for effective quality assessment and cross-organizational traceability.

The W3C PROV family of standards [PROV-overview] provides a widely adopted foundation for structured provenance representation. The Common Provenance Model (CPM) [CPF/ISO 23494-2] is an open extensible data model that extends PROV-DM with mechanisms for (i) interlinking provenance pieces across organizational boundaries, (ii) confidentiality-preserving traversal of distributed provenance, and (iii) extensibility for authenticity and non-repudiation of origin — all being aspects not directly addressed by PROV. Consequently, any CPM-based provenance record is PROV-DM-conformant by construction. The CPM was also standardised as *ISO 23494-2 Biotechnology — Provenance information model for biological material and data — Part 2: Common provenance model*, within the *ISO 23494* standard series on provenance of biological material and data. It is particularly suited to environments in which data is exchanged across organizational boundaries, such as the EHDS context.

2.2. List of Data Provenance controls

Based on the definitions above, we distinguish two main data provenance controls. The two controls are evaluated independently. Consequently, a dataset may pass Control #1 while scoring below the maximum on Control #2, and the two scores are reported separately.

Together, these controls assess whether the dataset is accompanied by sufficient documentation, and should be considered core controls for this dimension when applying the QUANTUM label.

1. Control #1 Source dataset-providing organization identified

Metric #1 - Dataset source documentation

Definition
Is the source of the dataset documented?

Recommended Measurement Approach
Ideally using a standard vocabulary as in DCAT-AP "dct:source; dct:creator; dct:contributor"

Weight
50%

Source is documented

Definition:

This control evaluates whether the organizations generating the source (raw) data are identified.

What to check:

Is the dataset accompanied by documentation that identifies the organizations responsible for generating the source data, from which the assessed data was derived?

Ways to measure:

This control can follow the following two levels:

- **Score 0 – Source dataset-providing organizations not documented**
No documentation is available.
- **Score 1 – Source dataset-providing organizations documented**
The organizations generating the source data from which the assessed data was derived are identified.

2. Control #2 Full provenance available in a standardized representation

Metric #2 - Processes and operation documentation

Definition
Are the processes and operations on the data documented?

Recommended Measurement Approach
Using PROV-O (PROV Ontology)

Weight
50%

Full documentation on data processes and operations complying with PROV-O standards

No documentation on data processes and operations

Some documentation on data processes and operations but not complying with PROV-O standards

3.3 Full documentation on data processes and operations complying with PROV-O standards

Definition:

This control evaluates whether all applicable provenance types — *data precursors provenance*, *data generation provenance*, and *data derivation provenance* — are documented according to CPM/PROV.

Applicability of each type is determined per the rules in Section 2.1.

To achieve the highest score, data provenance should be expressed in a machine-readable representation according to CPM/PROV. Data holders are encouraged to use CPM as a baseline in cases when data provenance documents processes that cross organizational boundaries.

What to check:

Is the assessed dataset accompanied by documentation that covers the complete chain of all applicable provenance types?

Non-applicable types can be documented as such, together with the justification (e.g., no biological precursor, no source, no post-generation processing), so that the pipeline shape remains determinable.

The information does not necessarily need to be part of the assessed data record, but can be available (with proper authorization) through linked provenance records accessible via references from the assessed dataset's provenance record.

For all events/processes, at minimum the type of event/process, methods, and responsible organizations must be documented. Identifiers of precursors and data may be omitted only in justified cases, such as legal or regulatory limitations. Any additional detail strengthens the provenance record.

Ways to measure:

This control can follow the following three levels:

- **Score 0 – No documentation**
No documentation is available.
- **Score 1 – Some documentation, non-standardized representation, or undetermined applicability**

All applicable provenance types are available only partially, information is not represented according to CPM/PROV, or the applicability of stage-specific provenance types for at least one sub-dataset cannot be determined from the record.

- **Score 2 – Full documentation complying with CPM/PROV**

The processes and operations applied to the data are fully documented and represented in a structured way consistent with CPM/PROV, and the applicability of stage-specific provenance types is determinable per sub-dataset.

2.3. How to apply the Data Provenance checks

This section illustrates how Control #1 and Control #2 are applied to the running example introduced in Section 2.1. The assessed dataset is the output of *Data integration and pre-processing (University)* and is composed of two sub-datasets: a clinical sub-dataset extracted from the HIS of Hospital A, and an imaging sub-dataset derived from samples processed and scanned at the Pathology lab. Control #1 and Control #2 are applied to the assessed dataset as a whole, but their evaluation requires reasoning per sub-dataset, because the applicability of each provenance type depends on the composition of the assessed dataset.

Applying Control #1

Control #1 requires that the organizations generating the source data, from which the assessed dataset was derived, are identified. The number of required generating organizations is determined by the composition of the assessed dataset. In the running example, the assessed dataset's composition implies two data generation operations: HIS Data Creation, which generates the clinical source data by manual data entry performed by a doctor, and Sample-derived data generation, which generates the imaging source data from prepared slides. Accordingly, the required set of generating organizations is {Hospital A, Pathology lab}.

- **Scenario #1 — Score 1:** The provenance documentation identifies Hospital A as the organization performing HIS Data Creation and the Pathology lab as the organization performing Sample-derived data generation. Both required generating organizations are present.

Verdict: Score 1.

- **Scenario #2 — Score 0:** The provenance documentation identifies Hospital A as the organization performing HIS Data Creation, but does not identify any organization for Sample-derived data generation. The generating-organization set is incomplete with respect to the assessed dataset's composition.

Verdict: Score 0.

Applying Control #2

Control #2 is applied by running the three checklists defined in Section 2.1 — *Data precursors provenance*, *Data generation provenance*, *Data derivation provenance* — against each sub-dataset of the assessed dataset and against the integration step that produces the assessed dataset from the sub-datasets. The score combines two axes: completeness of applicable elements across sub-datasets and the integration step, and representation (whether the record is structured according to CPM/PROV). The table below fixes, once, which elements are required per sub-dataset and for the integration step, and

what fully complete evidence would look like for the running example. The three scenarios after the table then vary the documentation state against this fixed reference.

Goal	Required provenance element	Applicability check	Evidence
<i>Data precursors provenance</i>			
	Patient/donor identifier(s)	Is the (sub-)dataset generated, directly or via predecessors, from biological material, and is pseudonymised identification permitted under applicable privacy and consent rules?	<i>Clinical sub-dataset:</i> N/A — no biological precursor. <i>Imaging sub-dataset:</i> Pseudonymised donor identifier attached to the provenance record of the acquired sample.
	Precursor (sample) identifier(s)	Are there precursors of the source, and is their identification permitted under applicable privacy and consent rules?	<i>Clinical sub-dataset:</i> N/A — no biological precursor. <i>Imaging sub-dataset:</i> Identifiers of the acquired sample and of every derived sample in the precursor chain (acquired sample → processed sample → slide used as source), together with their mutual relations.
	Precursor(s) (sample(s)) handling	Are there precursor-handling events relevant to the quality of the precursors, source data, or the assessed dataset?	<i>Clinical sub-dataset:</i> N/A — no biological precursor. <i>Imaging sub-dataset:</i> For each handling event (e.g., sample acquisition at Hospital B; sample processing at Pathology lab): event type, method reference (e.g. link to the SOP followed), and related timestamps.

	Responsible organization(s) identifier(s)	Are there organizations involved in precursor handling?	<p><i>Clinical sub-dataset:</i> N/A — no biological precursor.</p> <p><i>Imaging sub-dataset:</i> Identifiers of Hospital B (sample acquisition) and Pathology lab (sample processing).</p>
Data generation provenance			
	Source identifier	Does a source exist for the (sub-)dataset, and is pseudonymised identification of the source permitted under applicable privacy and consent rules?	<p><i>Clinical sub-dataset:</i> N/A — no physical source; the clinical data is itself source data, generated by manual data entry.</p> <p><i>Imaging sub-dataset:</i> Pseudonymised identifier of the slide used as the source of imaging.</p>
	Source organization identifier	Does a source exist for the (sub-)dataset, and was it provided by an identifiable organization?	<p><i>Clinical sub-dataset:</i> N/A — no physical source.</p> <p><i>Imaging sub-dataset:</i> Identifier of the Pathology lab as the organization that provided the slide as source.</p>
	Data generation step (Type / Method / Technology)	What was the data generation procedure applied, by what method, and with what technology?	<p><i>Clinical sub-dataset:</i> Type — manual data entry; Method — no applicable method for manual data entry; Technology — HIS software (provider, name, version).</p> <p><i>Imaging sub-dataset:</i> Type — scanning; Method — reference to the imaging SOP; Technology — scanner (manufacturer, model, serial number) and acquisition software (provider, name, version).</p>

	Responsible organization identifier	Which organization performed the data generation?	<i>Clinical sub-dataset:</i> Identifier of Hospital A (HIS Data Creation). <i>Imaging sub-dataset:</i> Identifier of the Pathology lab (Sample-derived data generation).
	Generated dataset identifier	What is the identifier of the dataset produced by the data generation step?	<i>Clinical sub-dataset:</i> Identifier of the clinical source dataset produced in the hospital during the Data Creation step. <i>Imaging sub-dataset:</i> Identifier of the image dataset produced during the Sample-derived data generation step.
Data derivation provenance			
	Preceding dataset(s) identifier(s)	Are there preceding datasets from which the assessed data is derived, and is their pseudonymised identification permitted?	<i>Clinical sub-dataset:</i> Identifiers of the clinical source dataset (input to HIS Data Extraction) and the extracted clinical dataset (input to Data annotation/cleaning). <i>Imaging sub-dataset:</i> Identifier of the image dataset (input to Data annotation). <i>Assessed dataset (integration step):</i> Identifiers of the cleaned clinical dataset and the annotated image dataset, both inputs to Data integration and pre-processing.

	Data processing step	What derivation steps were applied, of what type, using which tools and configurations?	<p><i>Clinical sub-dataset:</i> For HIS Data Extraction at Hospital A — type of operation (extraction) and reference to the extraction tool and configuration used; for Data cleaning at University — type of operation and reference to the cleaning tool/script and configuration used.</p> <p><i>Imaging sub-dataset:</i> For Data annotation at Pathology lab — type of operation and reference to the annotation tool and configuration used.</p> <p><i>Assessed dataset (integration step):</i> For Data integration and pre-processing at University — type of operation (integration and pre-processing) and reference to the integration tools/scripts and configuration used.</p>
	Responsible organization identifier	Which organizations were involved in the data derivation?	<p><i>Clinical sub-dataset:</i> Identifiers of Hospital A (HIS Data Extraction) and the University (Data cleaning).</p> <p><i>Imaging sub-dataset:</i> Identifier of the Pathology lab (Data annotation).</p> <p><i>Assessed dataset (integration step):</i> Identifier of the University (Data integration and pre-processing).</p>

- *Scenario #1 — Score 2:* All applicable elements in the table are documented for both sub-datasets and for the integration step, and the provenance record is expressed in a machine-readable representation according to CPM/PROV. The applicability of the stage-specific provenance types is determinable per sub-dataset from the record itself. Verdict: Score 2.

- Scenario #2 — Score 1 (representation axis):** All applicable elements in the table are documented for both sub-datasets and for the integration step, but the record is provided as prose documentation and spreadsheets rather than in a machine-readable representation according to CPM/PROV. Completeness is full; representation is non-standardised. Verdict: Score 1.
- Scenario #3 — Score 1 (completeness axis):** The provenance record is expressed in a machine-readable representation according to CPM/PROV, but at least one applicable element is missing — for example, *Precursor(s) (sample(s)) handling* for the imaging sub-dataset omits timestamps for the sample processing event, or the *Responsible organization identifier* for the integration step is absent. Representation is standardised; completeness is partial. Verdict: Score 1.

If no provenance documentation is available at all, Control #2 is scored 0.

Common Provenance Model example

Figure 2.4 outlines how required provenance information can be structured according to the CPM. Such a provenance record with an assigned identifier can be used to capture the required information in a standardized way, and be linked with other records to form a provenance chain. Each component of the chain can be potentially generated, stored, and managed independently by different organizations or organizational units.

3. Metadata Scope

3.1. Definition

QUANTUM defines the Metadata Scope dimension as “the availability, comprehensiveness, level of detail of metadata and data dictionaries that help users understand the data being used”.

This dimension specifically measures the descriptive layer of a dataset. It evaluates whether a user has enough contextual information to use the data before eventually consulting the original data holder.

It is assessed based on three specific criteria:

- Availability of a formal data dictionary or metadata record attached to the dataset, easily accessible for the potential users.
- Comprehensiveness of all the available variables covered by the metadata (see e.g. HealthDCAT-AP metadata specification as a reference).
- Level of detail, such as the use of a specific medical coding system (e.g., SNOMED-CT, ICD, ATC), the units of measurement (e.g., mmHg, mm) or the time range of collection.

3.2. List of Metadata Scope controls

Based on the definition above, we identified two types of metadata scope controls. To illustrate how each check operates, we use a consistent example throughout: a simplified dataset containing patient records from a fictional healthcare system. This ensures comparability and clarity across all examples.

For this example it is important to note that HealthDCAT-AP does not model variables but variable metadata is provided via a data dictionary, which is referenced from the dataset metadata as a `dcat:distribution`. In this example, the dataset is referenced as `dcat:dataset`, data dictionary as a `dcat:distribution`.

Table 1: A fictional data dictionary (`dcat:distribution`) that serves as metadata and accompanies the pretended health dataset (`dcat:dataset`)

Variable name (<code>dct:identifier</code>)	Description (<code>dct:description</code>)	Data type (<code>dct:format</code>)	Unit (<code>qudt:unit</code>)	Standard (<code>dct:conforms to</code>)
--	---	--	------------------------------------	--

patient_id	Unique patient identifier	xsd:string		
sex	Biological sex	xsd:boolean		
age	Age at admission	xsd:integer	unit:Year	
diagnosis_code	Primary diagnosis	xsd:string		ICD-10
medication	Code of the medicinal product administered in healthcare	xsd:string		
systolic_bp	Systolic blood pressure	xsd:integer	mmHg	
admission_date	Date of hospital admission	Datetime		

Types of metadata scope controls

1. Existence of comprehensive standardised metadata

Definition:

This check ensures that the provided metadata is compliant with a standardised metadata model (*e.g.* HealthDCAT-AP metadata specification), which mandates specific metadata field names and formats. Compliance with a recognised metadata standard is crucial for technical interoperability and harmonised dataset discovery and reuse. This acts as a minimum quality requirement for data providers and users. This check evaluates whether the metadata are non-standardised, partially, or fully compliant in this context refers to metadata that meet all mandatory requirements defined in the HealthDCAT-AP for dataset descriptions in the EHDS catalogue.

Applied to Case:

A fictional healthcare dataset is accompanied with a metadata record claiming compliance to the HealthDCAT-AP metadata specification.

What to check:

- ✓ Check 1: Is a formal metadata record provided and linked to the dataset?
- ✓ Check 2: Are prescribed formats, controlled vocabularies and field names respected?
- ✓ Check 3: Are all mandatory metadata fields required by the chosen standard present?
 - This is divided into two checks, the first calculating the overall percentage of metadata mandatory field completeness, and the second one giving a categorical representation to the result.

Ways to Measure:

Note : In this example, the dataset is referenced as dcat:dataset, data dictionary as a dcat:distribution

What to Check	How to Calculate	Applied Example
Presence of metadata record: Is the dataset described using HealthDCAT-AP compliant metadata record? Is a data dictionary referred to as a dataset distribution?	Verification that a Metadata record exists (Fail/Pass), by checking the expected HealthDCAT-AP compliant metadata elements are present.	The dataset includes a metadata record - data dictionary - modelled as a distribution: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Record dcat:dataset () exists : Pretended health dataset ✓ Record dcat:distribution exists ✓ Relevant metadata fields such as dct:identifier, dct:description are present Result: Pass
Are prescribed formats, controlled vocabularies and field names respected? Do variables use standard RDF properties?		Check that all variables use standard properties: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ dct:identifier ✓ dct:description ✓ dct:format ✓ Quantitative variables use qudt:unit <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Two coded standards, one missing a recognised reference Result: Partial adherence, as a coding reference is missing.

Mandatory fields completeness (%)	$(\text{Number of mandatory fields present} \div \text{total mandatory fields}) * 100 \%$	<p>Check whether the metadata covers all the required/mandatory fields of the selected metadata model. According to the selected metadata model for this example, HealthDCAT-AP, only two variables are mandatory at the dataset variable level (namely dct:identifier and cdt:description), as HealthDCAT-AP is a discovery metadata model. The other metadata fields provided in the example are either recommended or optional.</p> <p>Thus the mandatory fields completeness can be calculated as follows: $(2/2)*100\%=100\%$</p>
Standard compliance level	Categorical assessment (None / Partial / Full)	<p>Assess based on your criteria the categorical level for standard compliance, e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Fail: No metadata record or >70% fields present- Partial: Metadata exists, $\geq 70\%$ but <100% mandatory fields present- Pass: Metadata fully compliant with the standard

2. Existence of an exhaustive data dictionary at variable level

Definition:

This check ensures that the provided metadata is supported by an exhaustive data dictionary at variable level. The data dictionary is the granular reference document that explains every variable in the dataset, its meaning in plain language, permitted values or ranges, units of measurement, applicable international coding systems and ontologies, and rules for handling null or missing data.

Applied to Case:

A healthcare dataset is accompanied with a separate data dictionary document describing some - but not all - variables.

What to check:

Performing the following checks require evaluation variable by variable.

- ✓ Check 1: Are all variables in the dataset documented in the data dictionary (=variable coverage)?
- ✓ Check 2: Does each variable include sufficient descriptive detail?

- This check is divided into two parts. The first part monitors the proportional completeness of variable definitions, while the second part assesses the overall categorical completeness of the data dictionary.

Ways to Measure:

What to Check	How to Calculate	Applied Example
Variable coverage %	$(\text{Number of documented variables} \div \text{total variables}) \times 100$	<p>Calculate the coverage for documented variables.</p> <p>When comparing the data dictionary variable names to dataset data names (not presented in the example), we can establish that all variables that should be documented are documented.</p> <p>With this, we can calculate the coverage as follows:</p> $(7/7) \times 100\% = 100\%$ <p>Result: 100%</p>
Descriptive completeness	$(\text{Number of variables with complete documentation} \div \text{total number of variables}) \times 100$	<p>Calculate the completeness of the variable definitions.</p> <p>Here, all variables have a clear semantic definition, which is in plain language and understandable for the user.</p> <p>While checking for technical specification (unit +coding), we can see that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- sex is missing a value set and data type Boolean might not be optimal for it- medication is missing a reference standard (should be ATC)- Datetime data type not expressed as xsd:dateTime <p>This means, four variables are properly documented, and we can calculate the coverage as follows:</p> $(4/7) \times 100\% = 57,1\%$ <p>Result: 57,1%</p>
Overall dictionary completeness	Categorical (None / Partial / Full)	<p>Assess the overall completeness of the dataset's descriptive metadata (e.g., variable definitions, units, and coding).. As the data dictionary is missing a value set for sex and a coding reference standard for medication, the outcome</p>

		<p>is partial, even though the missing information could be deduced from the actual dataset. The data dictionary can be of high quality even though deemed partial.</p> <p>Result: Partial</p>
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3.3. How to apply the Metadata Scope checks

Metadata scope checks are applied before the actual data content analysis, as they determine whether the dataset can be correctly understood and interpreted. The controls are assessed at dataset and variable levels, and the results can be used as minimum quality gates (pass/fail), or scored inputs into overall data quality assessment. Metadata scope findings should be reviewed properly before downstream quality checks are applied. If the users cannot understand what the data represents, no level of data correctness can compensate for insufficient metadata scope.

Technical Data Quality Dimensions

1. Completeness

1.1. Definition

QUANTUM defines the completeness dimension as **“the degree to which all information that could be available is present in a particular dataset”**.

The definition refers to the presence of all necessary and expected data values in a dataset, ensuring its suitability for the intended purpose. This dimension can be evaluated across three key aspects:

- **Mandatory completeness**

This ensures that all mandatory fields, considered critical for the dataset’s intended use, are present.

Example: In a patient dataset, fields like patient ID, date of birth, and visit date are essential and must not be missing.

- **Conditional completeness**

This ensures that specific variables are complete when certain conditions or rules are met. These fields may not apply to all records but must be present when relevant criteria are satisfied.

Example: If a patient is prescribed medication, dosage and frequency must be recorded. For patients with allergies, the specific allergen and severity should be noted.

- **Cross-dataset completeness**

This ensures that all necessary data is available across related datasets and that all expected linkages or references between them are present and complete.

Example: In a hospital information system, if patient demographics are stored in one dataset and clinical records in another, every clinical record should have a corresponding patient ID in the demographic dataset.

1.2. List of completeness controls

Based on the definition in the previous section, we distinguish *three main types of completeness controls*. To illustrate how each check operates, we use a consistent example throughout: a simplified dataset containing patient records from a fictional healthcare system. This ensures comparability and clarity across all examples.

Table 1: Patient records

Patient ID	Patient Name	Date Of Birth	Diagnosis	Last Visit Date	Prescribed Medication
200000301	John Smith	5/14/1985	Hypertension	11/15/2023	Lisinopril
200000302	Sarah Johnson	7/21/1992	Asthma	10/10/2023	Albuterol
200000303	David Brown	<i>(empty)</i>	<i>(empty)</i>	<i>(empty)</i>	<i>(empty)</i>
200000304	Emily Davis	9/30/2000	Hypertension	01/22/2024	Amlodipine
200000305	Michael Lee	8/21/1959	High Cholesterol	<i>(empty)</i>	Atorvastatin
200000306	<i>(empty)</i>	11/2/1975	Diabetes Type 2	09/05/2023	Insulin

Types of completeness controls

3. Mandatory fields control

Definition:

This check ensures that all required fields, regardless of context, are completed across all records in the dataset. This check evaluates whether required data fields are empty or contain placeholders such as null, N/A, or 0 (if zero is not a valid value in that context). What is considered “mandatory” may vary depending on the data’s intended use, the research question, or more globally its purpose. It follows the Fit for purpose principles as described in the introduction.

Applied to Case:

Assume **Patient ID, Patient Name, Date of Birth and Prescribed Medication** are mandatory fields based on business rules defined by the dataset purpose.

Table 1: Patient records

Patient ID	Patient Name	Date Of Birth	Diagnosis	Last Visit Date	Prescribed Medication
200000301	John Smith	5/14/1985	Hypertension	11/15/2023	Lisinopril
200000302	Sarah Johnson	7/21/1992	Asthma	10/10/2023	Albuterol
200000303	David Brown	(empty)	(empty)	(empty)	(empty)
200000304	Emily Davis	9/30/2000	Hypertension	01/22/2024	(empty)
200000305	Michael Lee	8/21/1959	High Cholesterol	(empty)	Atorvastatin
200000306	(empty)	11/2/1975	Diabetes Type 2	09/05/2023	Insulin

What to check: Are the mandatory fields filled across the dataset?

- ✓ Check 1: Patient ID completeness
- ✓ Check 2: Patient name completeness
- ✓ Check 3: Date of birth completeness
- ✓ Check 4: Prescribed medication completeness

Ways to Measure:

What to Check	How to Calculate	Applied Example
% of records where all mandatory fields are filled	(Records with all mandatory fields filled / Total records) × 100	Check 1: Patient ID: 6/6 = 100% Check 2: Patient Name: 5/6 = 83.3% Check 3: Date Of Birth: 5/6 = 83.3% Check 4: Prescribed Medication: 5/6 = 83.3%
Average total completeness	(Sum of % completeness per Check) ÷ Number of checks)	Check 1: Patient ID: 6/6 = 100% Check 2: Patient Name: 5/6 = 83.3% Check 3: Date Of Birth: 5/6 = 83.3% Check 4: Prescribed Medication: 5/6 = 83.3% (100% + 83.3% + 83.3% + 83.3%) ÷ 4 = 87.5%

4. Conditional completeness control

Definition:

This control verifies whether a field is completed when a specific condition is present. That condition can be triggered either by the presence of a value in another field or by a specific value in that other field.

Applied to Cases:

Conditional completeness can be value-based or presence-based:

Value-based conditional completeness:

Check 1: If the diagnosis is "hypertension," then prescribed medication must be filled. In the dataset, two patients have a hypertension diagnosis.

Presence-based conditional completeness:

Check 2: If any value is entered into the prescribed medication field, then start date medication must also be filled.

Table 1: Patient records

Patient ID	Patient name	Date Of birth	Diagnosis	Last visit date	Prescribed medication	Start date medication
20000030 1	John Smith	5/14/1985	Hypertension	11/15/2023	Lisinopril	11/15/2023
20000030 2	Sarah Johnson	7/21/1992	Asthma	10/10/2023	Albuterol	11/10/2023
20000030 3	David Brown	(empty)	(empty)	(empty)	(empty)	(empty)
20000030 4	Emily Davis	9/30/2000	Hypertension	01/02/2024	(empty)	(empty)
20000030 5	Michael Lee	8/21/1959	High cholesterol	(empty)	Atorvastatin	(empty)
20000030 6	(empty)	11/2/1975	Diabetes Type 2	09/05/2023	Insulin	11/05/2023

What are the checks: Are the conditional fields filled across the dataset?

- ✓ Rule 1: Prescribed medication is filled when diagnosis = "hypertension".
- ✓ Rule 2: Start date medication is filled when prescribed medication is not empty.

Ways to measure:

What to check	How to calculate	Applied example
% of records where all conditional fields are filled	$(\text{Records with all conditional fields filled} / \text{Total records}) \times 100$	<p>- Check 1 (diagnosis = hypertension): applies to 2 patients → 1 filled, 1 missing → 50%</p> <p>- Check 2 (prescribed medication is filled): applies to 4 patients → 3 filled, 1 missing → 75%</p>
Total conditional completeness	$(\text{Total number of records with all applicable fields filled}) / (\text{Total number of records where at least one condition applies}) \times 100$	Total: 6 applicable records, 4 have all required fields filled → $4/6 = 66.7\%$
Average completeness per conditionally required field	$(\text{Sum of \% completeness per conditionally required field}) / \text{of conditionally required fields}$	<p>- Prescribed medication: $1/2 = 50\%$</p> <p>- Start date medication: $3/4 = 75\%$</p> <p>→ $(50\% + 75\%) / 2 = 62.5\%$</p>

5. Cross-dataset completeness control

Definition:

This control assesses whether all necessary records from a source dataset (can also be referred to as a “source-of-truth”) are present in a related dataset that depends on it. It ensures that all expected relationships or references between datasets are complete, and no records are unintentionally dropped or missing.

This kind of incompleteness often occurs when:

- Records are excluded due to incorrect query logic (e.g., using an Inner Join instead of a Left Join, which unintentionally removes source records with no match).
- Keys or references between datasets are broken or misaligned.
- Filtering, merging, or transformation steps omit data unintentionally during integration.

Note: Cross-dataset completeness checks often require access to both the **dataset being evaluated** and its **source dataset**. If the data holder of a derived dataset does not have access to the source-of-truth, it may be complex to perform this check directly.

Applied to cases:

The dataset in this case, *Table 2: Patient Records*, is the result of an automated extraction from another

system that contains the full *Table 1: Master Patient Records*. This master table holds the complete list of all registered patients. According to **business-defined rules**, the extraction process must ensure that all patient records from the master table are transferred in full and without omission.

Table 1: Master patient records

Patient ID	Patient name	Date of birth	Diagnosis	Last visit date	Prescribed medication
200000301	John Smith	5/14/1985	Hypertension	11/15/2023	Lisinopril
200000302	Sarah Johnson	7/21/1992	Asthma	10/10/2023	Albuterol
200000303	David Brown	6/01/1998	Migraine	10/05/2023	Sumatriptan
200000304	Emily Davis	9/30/2000	Hypertension	01/22/2024	Amlodipine
200000305	Michael Lee	8/21/1959	High cholesterol	07/05/2024	Atorvastatin
200000306	Annabelle Paul	11/2/1975	Diabetes type 2	09/05/2023	Insulin

Table 2: Patient records.

Patient ID	Patient name	Date of birth	Diagnosis	Last visit date	Prescribed medication
200000301	John Smith	5/14/1985	Hypertension	11/15/2023	Lisinopril
200000302	Sarah Johnson	7/21/1992	Asthma	10/10/2023	Albuterol
200000303	David Brown	(empty)	(empty)	(empty)	(empty)
200000304	Emily Davis	9/30/2000	Hypertension	01/22/2024	(empty)

What are the checks: Are all records in the master table (*Table 1*) represented in the extracted table (*Table 2*)?

- ✓ Check 1: Patient ID in table 2 completeness
- ✓ Check 2: Patient names in table 2 completeness
- ✓ Check 3: Dates of birth in table 2 completeness
- ✓ Check 4: Diagnoses in table 2 completeness
- ✓ Check 5: Last visit dates in table 2 completeness
- ✓ Check 6: Medications in table 2 completeness

How to measure:

What to check	How to calculate	Applied example
Column-level completeness per field	$(\text{Number of non-empty cells in column} / \text{Total rows}) \times 100$	<p>4 out of 6 Patient IDs are filled → 66.7%</p> <p>4 out of 6 Patient Names are filled → 66.7%</p> <p>3 out of 6 Dates of Birth are filled →</p>

		<p>50%</p> <p>3 out of 6 Diagnoses are filled → 50%</p> <p>3 out of 6 Last Visit Dates are filled → 50%</p> <p>2 out of 6 Medications are filled → 33.3%</p>
Overall average completeness across all columns	(Sum of all column completeness scores / Number of columns)	$(66.7 + 66.7 + 50 + 50 + 50 + 33.3) / 6 = 52.8\%$

1.3. How to apply the completeness checks

1. Critical vs non-critical completeness checks

Not all completeness issues have the same impact on the usability or reliability of a dataset. To support better interpretation of results and prioritization of quality improvements, we introduce a distinction between critical and non-critical completeness control.

Note: Criticality may vary by domain, system, or dataset purpose. While we propose default classifications, organizations are encouraged to define and document criticality based on their specific use cases.

Definition:

- **Critical checks** are considered essential for the dataset to serve its intended purpose. If they fail, the dataset (or relevant part of it) may be considered **unusable** or **unfit for use** until corrected. These typically involve missing values in mandatory fields or key rule violations.
- **Non-critical checks** are informative but less essential. If they fail, the dataset can still be used, though with reduced reliability or completeness. These checks highlight areas for improvement but do not necessarily block usage.

How to apply it:

The criticality classification is applied at the check (or rule) level, not per variable. A single variable can be involved in both critical and non-critical checks depending on the context.

Check type	Typical classification
Mandatory fields	● Critical
Conditional completeness	● Mixed (context-specific)
Cross-dataset completeness	● Usually non-critical

2. Practical scenarios

This section provides guidance on how to apply completeness checks depending on the structure and requirements of your dataset. The table below outlines typical scenarios based on three key elements: mandatory fields, conditional fields, and cross-dataset references.

Overview of the scenarios:

Scenario	Table type	Mandatory fields	Conditional fields	Checks
0	Source dataset	No	No	No completeness checks required
1	Source dataset	Yes	No	Mandatory fields checks
2	Source dataset	Yes	Yes	Mandatory fields checks Conditional completeness checks
3	Source dataset	No	Yes	Conditional completeness checks
4	Derived/Aggregated	No	No	Cross-dataset completeness checks
5	Derived/Aggregated	Yes	No	Cross-dataset completeness checks Mandatory fields checks
6	Derived/Aggregated	No	Yes	Cross-dataset completeness checks Conditional completeness checks

7	Derived/Aggregated	Yes	Yes	Cross-dataset completeness checks Mandatory fields checks Conditional completeness checks
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Worked example: Complete 7th scenario

This dataset is derived or aggregated from one or more data sources and includes mandatory fields, conditional fields, and cross-dataset references. The step-by-step guide below outlines how to apply a comprehensive completeness assessment.

Steps:

Step 1: Preparation starts with business rules

1. Identify business rules that define what “complete” means for the dataset.
 - a. Example: “Patient ID and date of birth must always be provided.”
 - b. Example: “If medication is prescribed, dosage must be recorded.”
2. Map each business rule to the relevant consistency control:
 - c. Mandatory values in specific fields → Mandatory fields completeness
 - d. Conditional requirements between fields → Conditional completeness
 - e. References that link to another dataset → Cross-dataset
3. Classify criticality for each rule:
 - f. Critical: Failure makes the dataset (or part of it) unusable for its intended purpose.
 - g. Non-critical: Failure reduces quality but does not block use.

Step 2: Define checks from controls

For each relevant control type, define one or more **technical checks** that measure compliance with the associated business rules.

Example: Control: Mandatory fields completeness

- ✓ Check 1: Patient ID is filled for all records.
- ✓ Check 2: Date of birth is populated for all records.

Example: Control: Conditional completeness

- ✓ Check 3: If medication is prescribed, dosage must be filled.

Example: Control: Cross-dataset completeness

- ✓ Check 4: All patient IDs in the extracted table are present in the master patient table.

Step 3: Calculate the checks

Calculate each check by applying the defined validation rules to the dataset and expressing the result as a quantitative metric. Ensure that calculations are reproducible and clearly linked to the underlying control and business rule.

Step 4: Aggregate scores per criticality

To assess the overall completeness of the dataset, calculate the following three scores:

- Critical completeness score = Average of all critical checks
Critical completeness = (Score of check 1 + check 2 + ...) / Number of critical checks
- Non-critical completeness score = Average of non-critical checks
Non-critical completeness = (Score of check 1 + check 2 + ...) / Number of non-critical checks
- Total completeness score = Average of all check results
Average completeness = (Mandatory fields % + Conditional fields % + Cross-dataset %) / 3

Step 5: Report the results in the completeness template

Document the results of all checks in the reporting template, including scores, applied rules, and criticality classifications to ensure transparency and traceability. Where applicable, include brief commentary on identified issues and potential remediation actions.

2. Consistency

2.1. Definition

QUANTUM defines the *consistency* dimension as “the degree to which data has attributes that are plausible and are uniform **with other data** and over time.”

In practice, this means ensuring that data values remain logically reasonable (**plausibility**) and consistently represented (**uniformity**) across different systems and throughout time.

Plausibility refers to whether individual data values are logically possible and medically realistic. Implausible values are those that fall outside expected ranges or violate domain knowledge. For example, a diagnosis of Alzheimer’s disease in a child would be clinically implausible. These types of errors indicate a breakdown in data capture or validation as they are not consistent together.

Uniformity, on the other hand, refers to the extent to which data remains consistent in format, value, and meaning across time and systems. A consistent dataset should not show contradictions when the same attribute is recorded in different places or at different times. For instance, a patient's blood type should be identical in the hospital laboratory system and in emergency room records. Likewise, attributes such as date of birth, sex, or nationality should not vary across records for the same individual. Uniformity also includes consistent use of codes, formats, and units. For instance, if gender is recorded, the dataset should apply a single, standardized code system rather than mixing formats like “M/F” and “Male/Female” in different records. Another common challenge involves timestamps. For example, if a dataset uses the format “YYYY-MM-DD”, that format should be applied consistently throughout. Mixing formats like “MM/DD/YYYY” or including time values in some records but not others can lead to inconsistencies in joins, filtering, or chronological comparisons. Likewise, failing to standardize time zones across systems can cause data to appear misaligned, even when values are technically correct.

Plausibility and conformity together enable consistency to focus on whether data elements agree with each other, rather than on whether each individual value is factually correct. Consistency asks: when you compare one variable to another, across systems, or over time, do they line up? Consistency checks do not validate the truth of a single value—that is the role of **accuracy**—but ensure there are no internal conflicts or mismatches.

2.2. List of consistency controls

Based on the definition in the previous, we distinguish *four* main types of consistency checks. Each targeting a different aspect of the definition. The checks include:

1. **Cross-field logical consistency:** Ensuring fields within a single record make sense together and follow business rules (no internal contradictions in a record).
2. **Syntactic consistency (intra-dataset formatting uniformity):** Ensuring data formatting and coding is uniform within a dataset.
3. **Cross-system consistency:** Ensuring the same data is consistent across different systems or data sources (no discrepancies for the same entity between systems).

- 4. **Longitudinal consistency (uniformity over time):** Ensuring stable attributes remain consistent across different versions of a dataset over time (no unexpected changes in historical data for the same entity).

Each of these consistency check types is detailed below with definitions, example checks, and ways to measure consistency. To illustrate how each check operates, we use an example throughout: a simplified dataset containing patient records from a fictional healthcare system. This ensures comparability and clarity across all examples.

Table 1: Patient records

Patient ID	Patient name	Date of birth	Sex	Age	Diagnosis	Pregnancy status	Weight (kg)	Height (cm)	BMI	Prescribed medication
100000001	Anna Stevens	03/12/1991	Female	32	Hypertension	Yes	75	170	26	Lisinopril
100000002	Robert White	08/22/1978	Male	45	Prostate cancer	No	82	175	26.8	Atorvastatin
100000003	John Adams	11/04/1989	Male	34	Pregnancy	Yes	70	180	21.6	Albuterol
100000004	Lily Martin	06/30/2011	Female	12	Alzheimer's disease	No	60	150	26.7	None
100000005	Grace Brown	12/15/1985	Female	38	None	No	600	220	124	Amlodipine

1. Cross-field logical consistency

Definition:

The cross-field logical consistency check verifies whether values in different fields within a single record are logically aligned with each other. It focuses on detecting internal contradictions between related fields, ensuring that data elements within the same record do not conflict and follow consistent internal logic.

Applied to case:

Using the patient dataset introduced above, the following **cross-field consistency checks** are applied. These checks evaluate whether values in different fields **within the same record** are logically aligned and do not contradict one another, based on clinical or domain-specific rules.

What to check:

Does the dataset comply with rule-based dependencies between fields?

- ✓ Consistency rule 1: If pregnancy status = Yes, then gender must be “female”
- ✓ Consistency rule 2: If diagnosis = pregnancy, then gender must be “female”.
- ✓ Consistency rule 3: If diagnosis = Alzheimer, then age should be ≥ 40.
- ✓ Consistency rule 4: If weight, height, and BMI are all present, then the BMI should mathematically match the formula: $BMI = \text{weight (kg)} / (\text{height in m})^2$

Ways to measure:

What to check	How to calculate	Applied example
Check-level consistency	For each check: (Number of compliant records / Number of applicable records) × 100	Check 1: 1 out of 2 applicable records respect the check → 50% Check 2: 1 out of 1 → 100% Check 3: 0 out of 1 → 0% Check 4: 3 out of 3 → 100%
Average logical consistency across checks	(Sum of all check-level consistency scores) / Number of checks	Check 1: 50% Check 2: 100% Check 3: 0% Check 4: 100% (50% + 100% + 0% + 100%) / 4 → 62.5%

2. Syntactic consistency:

Definition:

Syntactic consistency refers to the uniform use of formats, data types, and structural patterns within a

single field across all records. This check verifies that values are consistently structured in the same way throughout the dataset. It focuses on whether the same format is applied consistently to all entries, rather than whether the format aligns with an external standard or model.

Applied to case:

In the patient dataset, the following **syntactic consistency checks** are performed to ensure that the same format and structure is applied uniformly across values in each field.

What are the checks:

Are values within each field **consistently formatted** and **structured** in the same way across all records?

- ✓ Consistency rule 1: All date of birth values follow the same format, e.g., MM/DD/YYYY.
- ✓ Consistency rule 2: All patient IDs follow a consistent structure, e.g., 9-digit numeric values
- ✓ Consistency rule 3: All BMI values are expressed as numeric values
- ✓ Consistency rule 4: All weight and height entries are consistently recorded as positive numeric values

Ways to measure:

What to check	How to calculate	Applied example
Field-level consistency	For each check: (Number of records with syntactically consistent values / Total applicable records) × 100	R1: 5 out of 5 → 100% R2: 5 out of 5 → 100% R3: 5 out of 5 → 100% R4: 5 out of 5 → 100%
Average syntactic consistency	(Sum of all rule-level consistency scores) / Number of checks	R1: 5 out of 5 → 100% R2: 5 out of 5 → 100% R3: 5 out of 5 → 100% R4: 5 out of 5 → 100% (100% + 100% + 100% + 100%) / 4 → 100%

3. Cross-system consistency check

Definition:

The cross-system consistency check evaluates whether the **same data values are used consistently** across different systems or datasets for the same entity. It focuses on identifying discrepancies in **shared**

fields — such as diagnosis, medication, or vital signs — that should remain aligned between systems when referring to the same individual.

Note: Cross-system consistency checks often require access to both the **dataset being evaluated** and its **source dataset**. If the data holder of a derived dataset does not have access to the source-of-truth, it may be complex to perform this check directly.

Applied to case:

To assess cross-system consistency, we compare the values of **shared fields** for patients that appear in both the **patient records table** and an **external medication system**. The goal is to verify that the **same values are used consistently** across datasets when referring to the same patient.

In this example, we check whether the **prescribed medication** field contains **matching values** across the two systems for each patient ID that exists in both sources.

Table 1: Patient records

Patient ID	Patient name	Date of birth	Sex	Age	Diagnosis	Pregnancy status	Weight (kg)	Height (cm)	BMI	Prescribed medication
100000001	Anna Stevens	03/12/1991	Female	32	Hypertension	Yes	75	170	26	Lisinopril
100000002	Robert White	08/22/1978	Male	45	Prostate cancer	No	82	175	26.8	Atorvastatin
100000003	John Adams	11/04/1989	Male	34	Pregnancy	Yes	70	180	21.6	Albuterol
100000004	Lily Martin	06/30/2011	Female	12	Alzheimer's disease	No	60	150	26.7	None

100000005	Grace Brown	12/15/1985	Female	38	None	No	600	220	124	Amlodipine

Table 2: Medication system table (External source)

Patient ID	Prescribed medication
100000001	Lisinopril
100000002	Atorvastatin
100000003	Albuterol
100000004	None
100000005	Metformin

What to check:

- ✓ Are shared values (e.g. medications) **used consistently** for the same patients across different datasets or systems?

Ways to measure:

What to check	How to calculate	Applied example
Field-level consistency	For each shared field: $(\text{Number of matching values across datasets} / \text{Total number of shared records}) \times 100$	Prescribed medication: 4 of 5 patient records match → 80% consistency
Average cross-system consistency across fields	$(\text{Sum of field-level consistency scores}) / \text{Number of shared fields}$	If only one field is evaluated (medication), average = 80%

4. Longitudinal consistency check (uniformity over time)

Definition:

The longitudinal consistency check evaluates whether values in fields expected to remain stable over time are consistently recorded across multiple time-stamped records for the same entity within a single dataset.

Applied to case:

To assess longitudinal consistency, we examine values in fields that are expected to remain **unchanged over time** across multiple **encounters** for the same patient within a single dataset. In this example, we detect whether stable attributes like **Blood type and date of birth** are **consistently recorded** throughout the patient's history.

Table 3: Patient history

Patient ID	Encounter data	Date of birth	Blood type	Diagnosis
100000001	2024-11-01	03/12/1991	A+	Hypertension
100000001	2025-01-10	03/12/1991	A+	Check-up
100000002	2024-12-05	08/22/1978	B+	Diabetes
100000002	2025-02-01	08/22/1978	O+	Follow-up
100000003	2025-01-15	11/04/1989	O-	Asthma
100000003	2025-03-20	11/04/1989	O-	ER visit

What to check:

- ✓ Do values in stable fields such as **date of birth** and **blood type** remain **consistent across all encounters** for each patient within the dataset?

Ways to measure:

What to check	How to calculate	Applied example
Field-level consistency	For each stable field: (Number of matching values across encounters / Total number of records) × 100	Date of Birth: 6 of 6 match → 100% Blood Type: 5 of 6 match → 83.3%
Average longitudinal consistency	(Sum of field-level consistency scores) / Number of fields	(100% + 83.3%) / 2 → 91.7%

2.3. How to apply the consistency checks

1. Critical vs non-critical consistency checks

Not all consistency issues have the same impact on the usability or reliability of a dataset. To support better interpretation of results and prioritization of quality improvements, we introduce a distinction between **critical** and **non-critical** consistency checks.

Definition:

- **Critical checks** are considered essential for the dataset to serve its intended purpose.
- **Non-critical checks** are informative but less essential

How to apply it:

The criticality classification is applied at the check (or rule) level, not per variable. A single variable can be involved in both critical and non-critical consistency checks depending on the context.

Note: Criticality may vary by domain, system, or dataset purpose. While we propose default classifications, organizations are encouraged to define and document criticality based on their specific use cases.

Check type	Typical classification
Cross-field logical consistency	● Critical
Cross-system consistency	● Mixed (context-specific)
Longitudinal consistency	● Usually non-critical (context-specific)

Syntactic consistency	● Usually Non-Critical
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2. Practical scenarios

This section provides guidance on how to apply consistency checks depending on the structure and characteristics of your dataset. The table below outlines common scenarios based on whether the dataset includes internal rules, formatting requirements, statistical patterns, or values that appear across systems.

Overview of the scenarios:

Scenario	Dependent fields? <i>Do some fields rely on others (e.g. rule-based logic)?</i>	Structured formats? <i>Are some fields expected to follow a consistent format (e.g. IDs, dates)?</i>	Shared across systems? <i>Are some fields also present in other datasets or systems?</i>	Repeated records over time? <i>Are there multiple time-stamped entries for the same entity?</i>	Checks to apply
0	No	No	No	No	No consistency checks
1	Yes	No	No	No	Cross-field logical Consistency
2	No	Yes	No	No	Syntactic consistency
3	Yes	Yes	No	No	Cross-field logical consistency Syntactic consistency
4	No	No	Yes	No	Cross-system consistency

5	Yes	No	Yes	No	Cross-field logical consistency Cross-system consistency
6	No	Yes	Yes	No	Syntactic consistency Cross-system consistency
7	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Cross-field logical consistency Syntactic consistency Cross-system consistency
8	No	No	No	Yes	Longitudinal consistency
9	Yes	No	No	Yes	Cross-field logical consistency Longitudinal consistency
10	No	Yes	No	Yes	Syntactic consistency Longitudinal consistency
11	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Cross-field logical consistency Syntactic consistency Longitudinal consistency
12	No	No	Yes	Yes	Cross-system consistency Longitudinal consistency
13	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Cross-field logical consistency Cross-system consistency Longitudinal consistency
14	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Syntactic consistency Cross-system consistency Longitudinal consistency
15	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	All four checks: Cross-field logical consistency Syntactic consistency

					Cross-system consistency Longitudinal consistency
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Worked example: Complete 15th scenario – Fully structured dataset with logic, formatting, system links, and time-based records.

Steps:

Step 1: Preparation starts with business rules

1. Identify business rules that define what “consistent” means for the dataset.
 - a. Example: “If pregnancy status = Yes, gender must be female.”
 - b. Example: “Date of birth must be in the same format across all records.”
2. Map each business rule to the relevant consistency control:
 - a. Logical dependencies → Cross-field logical consistency
 - b. Syntactic format requirements → Syntactic consistency
 - c. Shared values across systems → Cross-system consistency
 - d. Stable attributes over time → Longitudinal consistency
3. Classify critically for each rule:
 - h. Critical: Failure makes the dataset (or part of it) unusable for its intended purpose.
 - i. Non-critical: Failure reduces quality but does not block use.

Step 2: Define checks from controls

For each relevant control type, define one or more **technical checks** that measure compliance with the associated business rules.

Example: Control = Cross-field logical consistency

- ✓ Rule 1: If pregnancy status = Yes, gender must be female.
- ✓ Rule 2: If Diagnosis = Pregnancy, gender must be female.

Step 3: Calculate the checks

Calculate each check by applying the defined validation rules to the dataset and expressing the result as a quantitative metric. Ensure that calculations are reproducible and clearly linked to the underlying control and business rule.

Step 4: Aggregate scores per criticality

To assess the overall consistency of the dataset, calculate the following three scores:

- Critical consistency score = Average of all critical checks

Critical consistency = (Score of Check 1 + Check 2 + ...) / Number of critical Checks

- Non-critical completeness score = Average of non-critical checks

Non-critical consistency = (Score of Check 1 + Check 2 + ...) / Number of non-critical checks

- Total consistency score = Average of all check results

Average consistency = (Cross-dataset % + Mandatory fields % + Conditional fields %) / 3

Step 5: Report the results in the consistency template

Document the results of all checks in the reporting template, including scores, applied rules, and criticality classifications to ensure transparency and traceability. Where applicable, include brief commentary on identified issues and potential remediation actions.

3. Accuracy

3.1. Definition

QUANTUM defines the accuracy dimension as “*the degree to which **observations** correctly **describe** what it was designed to measure*”.

In practice, accuracy assesses whether a data value correctly represents the real-world entity or fact it is intended to capture. It considers whether the information is factually correct, error-free, and can be independently verified using a reliable source or reference. High data accuracy enables real-world entities to be correctly identified and to function as intended within processes or systems.

3.2. List of accuracy controls

Based on the definition above, we distinguish four *main types of accuracy checks*. To illustrate how each check operates, we use a consistent example throughout: a simplified dataset containing patient records from a fictional healthcare system.

Table 1: Patient records

Patient ID	Patient name	Date of birth	Gender	Age	Diagnosis	Pregnancy status	Weight (kg)	Height (cm)	BMI	Prescribed medication
100000001	Anna Stevens	03/12/1991	Female	32	Hypertension	Yes	75	170	26	Lisinopril
100000002	Robert White	08/22/1978	Male	45	Prostate cancer	No	82	175	26.8	Atorvastatin
100000003	John Adams	11/04/1989	Male	34	Pregnancy	Yes	70	180	21.6	None
100000004		06/30/2011	Female	12	Alzheimer's disease	No	60	150	26.7	None

	Lily Martin									
10000000 5	Grace Brown	12/15/198 5	Female	38	None	No	600	220	124	Amlodipine

1. Real-world alignment

Definition:

This check assesses whether values in the dataset are realistic and clinically plausible⁴, based on known medical, physical, or biological limits. It verifies that values could reasonably occur in the real world, regardless of their format or internal consistency.

Applied to case:

We assess selected fields in the *patient records* dataset against established real-world reference ranges. Values falling outside acceptable human or clinical thresholds are flagged as inaccurate.

What to check:

Are the values clinically and physically plausible, and can they be verified against known real-world standards?

- ✓ Rule 1: *If age is present, it must be between 0 and 120 years.*
- ✓ Rule 2: *If BMI is present, it must be less than or equal to 60.*
- ✓ Rule 3: *If weight is present, it must be less than or equal to 300 kg.*
- ✓ Rule 4: *If pregnancy status = Yes, then gender must be "female".*

Ways to measure:

What to Check	How to Calculate	Applied Example
Field-level accuracy	(Number of matches / Total values compared) × 100	R1: 5/5 = 100% R2: 4/5 = 80% R3: 4/5 = 80% R4: 4/5 = 0%
Average real-world accuracy	(Sum of field-level accuracy scores) / Number of fields	(100% + 80% + 80% + 0%) / 4 = 65%

⁴ Plausibility concept introduced in the consistency dimension.

2. Reperformance check

Definition:

This check assesses whether a field in the dataset is accurate by independently recalculating it using other related data fields or an established calculation method. A separate, validated formula or logic is applied to verify whether the stored values (e.g., BMI, age, dosage) were correctly derived. This comparison helps detect manual entry errors, system miscalculations, or formula inconsistencies.

Applied to case:

We verify the Age values in the patient records dataset by independently recalculating them using the date of birth and a fixed reference date (01/01/2024). This allows us to assess whether the entered age value accurately represents what it should be when recalculated using another related field (date of birth). If the recalculated age differs from the recorded value by more than one year, the entry is flagged as inaccurate.

Patient ID	Date of birth	Recorded age	Recalculated age (as of 01/01/2024)	Deviation	Accurate?
100000001	03/12/1991	32	32	0	yes
100000002	08/22/1978	45	45	0	yes
100000003	11/04/1989	34	34	0	yes
100000004	06/30/2011	12	12	0	yes
100000005	12/15/1985	38	38	0	yes

What to check:

- ✓ Does the entered value accurately represent what it should be when recalculated using other related fields or an independent calculation method?

Ways to measure:

What to check	How to calculate	Applied example
Field-level accuracy	(Number of correct recalculations / Total values checked) × 100	Date of Birth: 6 of 6 match = 100%
Average recalculation accuracy	(Sum of field-level accuracy scores) / Number of checks	100%

3. Proxy estimation accuracy check

Definition:

This check assesses the accuracy or reasonableness of a field's value by comparing it to a **proxy-derived estimate**. It is applied when **no direct verification method or authoritative source** is available, but related fields allow for a plausible estimate. While similar in approach to a performance check, this method does **not aim to validate against a known formula**, but rather to evaluate whether the value falls within a reasonable range based on **indirect indicators or expected patterns**.

Applied to case:

In the patient records dataset, we estimate whether the BMI values are reasonable by using weight and height to calculate a proxy value.

Even if we cannot confirm whether the stored BMI values were calculated correctly (e.g., due to rounding or unknown internal system logic), we use a standard BMI formula as a proxy estimate to check whether the stored values are within an acceptable deviation margin.

$$\text{Proxy BMI} = \text{Weight (kg)} / (\text{Height (m)})^2$$

Values are considered acceptable if the difference between the recorded and proxy BMI is ≤ 0.1

Patient ID	BMI (Recorded)	Weight (kg)	Height (cm)	BMI (Proxy)	Difference	Within margin?
100000001	26.0	75	170	25.95	0.05	YES (≤ 0.1)
100000002	26.8	82	175	26.78	0.02	YES
100000003	21.6	70	180	21.60	0.00	YES
100000004	26.7	60	150	26.67	0.03	YES
100000005	124	600	220	124.38	0.38	NO (> 0.1)

What to check:

- ✓ Does the recorded value reasonably approximate what it should be when **estimated using a known proxy calculation** from other related fields?

Ways to measure:

What to check	How to calculate	Applied example
Proxy accuracy per rule	(Records within accepted deviation margin / Total applicable records) × 100	4 of 5 BMI values are within margin → 80%
Average proxy accuracy	If multiple proxy rules are applied, take the average	Only BMI used → 80%

4. Statistical accuracy checks

Distribution consistency

Definition:

This check evaluates whether the statistical distribution of a variable in the dataset aligns with expected or natural patterns.

Applied to case:

In the patient dataset, the syntactic rules apply.

What to check:

Does the dataset contain variables whose distributions align with expected clinical, biological, or statistical patterns?

- ✓ Rule 1: Age should follow a right-skewed or bell-shaped distribution in general populations
- ✓ Rule 2: BMI should fall mostly within the normal-to-obese range (18.5–40)
- ✓ Rule 3: Weight should increase with height (positive correlation expected)
- ✓ Rule 4: The overall distribution of height should reflect typical adult human range (150–200 cm)

Ways to measure:

What to check	How to calculate	Applied example
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Rule-level consistency	Evaluate whether the distribution meets the expected pattern (quantitatively or visually)	R1: 4 adults, 1 child → right-skewed → Consistent R2: BMI 124 → Inconsistent R3: Weak correlation → Inconsistent R4: One height = 150 cm, others plausible → Consistent
Score (per rule)	Assign a score of 100% if the distribution is acceptable, 0% if clearly inconsistent, or partial if borderline	R1: 100% R2: 0% R3: 0% R4: 100%
Average consistency	(Sum of all rule-level consistency scores) / Number of rules	R1: 100% R2: 0% R3: 0% R4: 100% (100% + 0% + 0% + 100%) / 4 → 50%

5. Presence of outliers:

Definition:

This check identifies whether the dataset contains extreme values that deviate significantly from the overall pattern. While some outliers may be valid (e.g., rare but real clinical cases), others can indicate data entry errors, system issues, or inconsistencies in how data was collected or recorded.

Applied to case:

We assess whether any numerical variables include outliers that are statistically or clinically implausible, and whether they are addressed.

What to check:

Does the dataset contain extreme values that fall outside expected bounds for human populations, and are such outliers minimal or appropriately justified?

- ✓ Rule 1: Age should fall within a reasonable clinical range (e.g., 0–120 years)
- ✓ Rule 2: BMI values above 60 are highly unlikely and should be reviewed

- ✓ Rule 3: Weight should fall within a plausible human range (e.g., 2–300 kg)
- ✓ Rule 4: Height values below 100 cm or above 220 cm should be flagged

Ways to measure:

What to check	How to calculate	Applied example
Rule-level consistency	(% of records within the expected range for that variable)	R1 (Age): All values 12–45 → 100% R2 (BMI): One value = 124 → 0% R3 (Weight): One value = 600 kg → 0% R4 (Height): All between 150–220 cm → 100%
Average outlier consistency	(Sum of rule scores) / Number of rules	R1: 100% R2: 0% R3: 0% R4: 100% (100% + 0% + 0% + 100%) / 4 → 50%

6. Expert-based check

Definition:

This check involves having a **domain expert manually review values** to assess whether they appear reasonable, complete, and correct. It is particularly useful when automated rules or reference sources are unavailable, incomplete, or too rigid.

Applied to case:

A clinical expert reviews the patient records dataset and flags any values that don't align with typical expectations for diagnosis-medication combinations, age appropriateness, or clinical plausibility.

Patient ID	Diagnosis	Prescribed medication	Expert verdict

10000000 1	Hypertension	Lisinopril	Accurate
10000000 2	Prostate cancer	Atorvastatin	Acceptable (used for cholesterol management)
10000000 3	Pregnancy	None	Inaccurate (male patient with pregnancy diagnosis)
10000000 4	Alzheimer's disease	None	Reasonable (medication may not be recorded)
10000000 5	None	Amlodipine	Inaccurate (medication with no diagnosis)

How to measure:

What to check	How to calculate	Applied example
% expert-confirmed values	$(\text{Expert-approved records} / \text{Total reviewed records}) \times 100$	3 of 5 records deemed accurate → 60%

3.3. How to apply the accuracy checks

1. Critical vs non-critical accuracy checks

Not all **accuracy issues** have the same impact on the usability or reliability of a dataset. To support better interpretation of results and prioritization of quality improvements, we distinguish between **critical** and **non-critical** accuracy checks.

Definition:

- **Critical checks** are considered essential for the dataset to serve its intended purpose.
- **Non-critical checks** are informative but less essential.

How to apply it:

The criticality classification is applied at the check (or rule) level, not per variable. A single variable can be involved in both critical and non-critical consistency checks depending on the context.

Note: Criticality may vary by domain, system, or dataset purpose. While we propose default classifications, organizations are encouraged to define and document criticality based on their specific use cases.

Check type	Typical classification
Real-world alignment	● Critical
Reperformance check	● Mixed (context-specific)
Proxy estimation	● Mixed (Context-specific)
Statistical distribution	● Usually non-critical
Outlier detection	● Mixed (context-specific)
Expert-based review	● Mixed (context-specific)

2. Practical scenarios

This section provides hands-on guidance to help you apply the accuracy checks outlined in list of accuracy controls. It is organized into practical scenarios. *Choose the one scenario that best matches your dataset's context — and follow the corresponding checks.*

If one of the questions in the table below receives a positive answer, then apply the controls. If the questions receive a negative answer then apply the steps following the table below.

Step	Key question	Controls
1	Can the value be independently recalculated using related fields and a known formula? (e.g., age from date of birth)	Recalculation / Reperformance + Real-world alignment
2	Can the value be estimated using proxy fields, and can outliers/plausibility be checked, with expert input available to review edge cases?	Proxy estimation + Outliers/Plausibility + Expert + Real-world alignment

3	Can the value be estimated using proxy fields, and can plausibility/outliers be evaluated (but no expert is available)?	Proxy estimation + Outliers/Plausibility + Real-world alignment
4	Can the value be estimated from a proxy field, but no other validation is possible?	Proxy estimation + Real-world alignment
5	No proxy available, but plausibility checks (e.g. outlier thresholds) and expert input are available?	Outliers/Plausibility + Expert + Real-world alignment
6	Only outlier or plausibility checks possible (no proxy, no expert)?	Outliers/Plausibility + Real-world alignment
7	None of the above, but expert review is available?	Expert-based Review + Real-world alignment
8	None of the above?	No accuracy checks applicable

Worked example:**Steps:****Step 1: Preparation starts with business rules**

1. Identify business rules that define what “accurate” means for the dataset.
 - j. Example: “Age must correctly match date of birth as of a reference date.”
 - k. Example: “Weight must be within the clinically plausible human range (2–300 kg).”
 - l. Example: “If diagnosis = pregnancy, gender must be female.”
2. Map each business rule to the relevant consistency control:
 - m. Real-world alignment → Rule checks against known physical, clinical, or logical limits.
 - n. Reperformance check → Recalculation of derived fields (e.g., age from date of birth).
 - o. Proxy estimation accuracy → Comparison against proxy-derived estimates (e.g., BMI from weight and height).
 - p. Statistical accuracy → Check distributions, expected correlations, and outliers.
 - q. Expert-based review → Manual verification by domain experts.

3. Classify criticality for each rule:

- r. Critical: Failure makes the dataset (or part of it) unusable for its intended purpose.
- s. Non-critical: Failure reduces quality but does not block use.

Step 2: Define checks from controls

For each control type, define one or more **technical checks** that measure compliance with the associated business rules.

Example: Control = Real-world alignment

- ✓ Rule 1: Weight \leq 300 kg.
- ✓ Rule 2: BMI \leq 60.

Example: Control = Reperformance

- ✓ Check 3: Recorded age matches recalculated age (± 1 year tolerance).

Step 3: Calculate the checks

Calculate each check by applying the defined validation rules to the dataset and expressing the result as a quantitative metric. Ensure that calculations are reproducible and clearly linked to the underlying control and business rule.

Step 4: Aggregate scores per criticality

To assess the overall consistency of the dataset, calculate the following three scores:

- Critical accuracy score = Average of all critical checks

Critical accuracy = (Score of Check 1 + Check 2 + ...) / Number of critical checks

- Non-critical accuracy score = Average of non-critical checks

non-critical accuracy = (Score of Check 1 + Check 2 + ...) / Number of non-critical checks

- Total accuracy score = Average of all check results

Average accuracy = (Score Check 1 + Score Check 2 + ...) / Total Number of checks

Step 5: Report the results in the accuracy template

Document the results of all checks in the reporting template, including scores, applied rules, and criticality classifications to ensure transparency and traceability. Where applicable, include brief commentary on identified issues and potential remediation actions.

4. Coherence

4.1. Definition

QUANTUM defines the coherence dimension as *“the dimension that expresses how different parts of the dataset are uniform in their representation and meaning over time, such as formats, semantics (stability of the data models), and methods.”*

While consistency focuses on whether data values remain consistent **between or across systems or time for the same data (internal stability)**, coherence addresses whether the *underlying definitions, formats, coding systems, and data models* remain stable or are changed in a controlled, documented way (**external alignment**).

This ensures that:

- Formats and units are stable, and changes are version-controlled (*e.g.*, consistent date structures or medical coding standards).
- Semantic definitions are applied consistently across departments, systems, or time (*e.g.*, “follow-up visit” means the same thing in all contexts).
- Data model structures, calculation methods, and classification schemes remain aligned, or changes are justified and documented.

Changes in business rules, variable definitions, or semantic logic without documentation or version control can lead to coherence issues and interpretation errors.

Example: Medical coding systems such as SNOMED CT are updated on a regular basis, with certain codes becoming inactive and replaced by new codes. For instance, a dataset may contain the SNOMED CT code **44054006** representing “Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.” In a subsequent release of the coding system, this code may be retired and superseded by the new code **TBD12345 (hypothetical)** that carries the same clinical meaning. To maintain coherence, the dataset would be updated to replace the retired code with its valid successor, ensuring that the semantic intent remains unchanged. This change should be traceable through appropriate documentation, thereby preserving the stability of meaning over time and enabling consistent interpretation by data users.

4.2. List of coherence controls

We distinguish **two main types** of coherence controls. To illustrate how each control operates, we use the same reference dataset of fictional patient records.

1. Coherence control on uniform meaning over time

Definition:

This control evaluates whether the **definitions, meanings, and calculation methods** of variables remain stable across different versions of a dataset or over time. It checks whether **the meaning and representation of variables are preserved over time**, across systems or contexts (e.g. "pregnancy status" means the same thing in 2023 as in 2024, terminology for a prescribed medication changed due to a regulation,...).

If changes must occur (for example, modifying a code list, field definition, or data format), they are considered coherent if modifications are properly versioned, thoroughly documented, and effective dates are recorded. This ensures that all stakeholders can interpret historical and current data correctly, trace changes, and maintain longitudinal comparability.

Applied to case:

Table 1: Patient Records 2024

Patient ID	Patient name	Date of birth	Diagnosis	Last visit date	Prescribed medication
200000301	John Smith	5/14/1985	Hypertension	11/15/2024	Lisinopril
200000302	Sarah Johnson	7/21/1992	Asthma	10/10/2024	Albuterol
200000303	David Brown	(empty)	Type 2 diabetes	09/05/2024	(empty)

Table 2 : Patient records 2025

Patient ID	Patient name	Date of birth	Diagnosis	Last visit date	Prescribed medication
200000304	Emily Davis	9/30/2000	Hypertension	01/22/2025	(empty)
200000305	Michael Lee	8/21/1959	High cholesterol	(empty)	Atorvastatin
200000306	(empty)	11/2/1975	Diabetes type 2	09/05/2025	Insulin

What are the checks:

- ✓ Do variable values across time and within records preserve consistent and logical meaning?

Ways to measure:

What to check	How to calculate	Applied example
% of time-stable values	$(\text{Number of value} / \text{Total checked}) \times 100$	Diagnosis phrasing changed for the diabetes records of 1996 & 2023, if the phrasing was documented then Coherence is still valid.

2. Coherence control on uniform format over time**Definition:**

This control verifies that **data formats and classification standards** (e.g. ICD, LOINC, SNOMED) have remained stable or were changed in a version-controlled and documented way.

Applied to case:

We review diagnostic coding formats. For instance, if some records from 2023 use ICD-9 and others use ICD-10 without metadata to explain the transition, this indicates incoherence.

Another example can be the transition from a YYYY/MM/DD format to a MM/DD/YYYY format that would not have been documented.

Table 1: Patient records 2024

Patient ID	Patient name	Date of birth	Diagnosis	Last visit date	Prescribed medication
200000301	John Smith	5/14/1985	Hypertension	11/15/2024	Lisinopril
200000302	Sarah Johnson	7/21/1992	Asthma	10/10/2024	Albuterol
200000303	David Brown	<i>(empty)</i>	<i>Type 2 diabetes</i>	09/05/2024	<i>(empty)</i>

Table 2 : Patient records 2025

Patient ID	Patient name	Date of birth	Diagnosis	Last visit date	Prescribed medication
200000304	Emily Davis	2000/30/12	Hypertension	2025/22/10	<i>(empty)</i>
200000305	Michael Lee	1959/10/02	High cholesterol	<i>(empty)</i>	Atorvastatin
200000306	<i>(empty)</i>	1975/11/02	<i>Diabetes type 2</i>	2025/05/02	Insulin

What to check:

- ✓ Check 1 : Coherence between date formatting

Ways to measure:

What to check	How to calculate	Applied example
% of internally coherent records	$(\text{Number of records with aligned values} / \text{Total records}) \times 100$	The date format change between 2 reports – If it was not described / version, this will give of 0% for the check

4.3. How to apply coherence checks

1. Critical vs non-critical coherence checks

Not all coherence issues have the same impact on the interpretability or usability of a dataset. To support prioritization, checks are classified as either **critical** or **non-critical** depending on whether a failure would make the data unusable for its intended purpose or simply reduce its comparability over time.

Definition:

- Critical checks** are considered essential for the dataset to serve its intended purpose. If they fail, the dataset (or relevant part of it) may be considered **unusable** or **unfit for use** until corrected. These typically involve missing values in mandatory fields or key rule violations.
- Non-critical checks** are informative but less essential. If they fail, the dataset can still be used, though with reduced reliability or completeness. These checks highlight areas for improvement but do not necessarily block usage.

How to apply it:

The criticality classification is applied at the check (or rule) level, not per variable. A single variable can be involved in both critical and non-critical checks depending on the context. Criticality may vary by domain, system, or dataset purpose. While we propose default classifications, organizations are encouraged to define and document criticality based on their specific use cases.

Check type	Typical classification
Uniform meaning over time	● Critical
Uniform format over time	● Mixed (context-specific)

2. Practical scenarios

Steps:

Step 1: Preparation starts with business rules

1. Identify business rules that define what “coherence” means for the dataset.
 - t. Example (uniform meaning): “The definition of ‘follow-up visit’ must remain identical across all dataset versions.”
 - u. Example (uniform format): “All diagnosis codes must follow ICD-10 after 2021, with any changes documented and version-controlled.”
2. Map each business rule to the relevant consistency control:
 - v. **Uniform meaning over time** → Stability of definitions, semantics, and calculation logic.
 - w. **Uniform format over time** → Stability of formats, coding systems, and classification schemes, or documented version-controlled changes.
3. Classify criticality for each rule:
 - x. Critical: Failure makes the dataset (or part of it) unusable for its intended purpose.
 - y. Non-critical: Failure reduces quality but does not block use.

Step 2: Define checks from controls

For each control type, define one or more **technical checks** that measure compliance with the associated business rules.

Example: Control = Uniform meaning over time

- ✓ Check 1: “Pregnancy status” definition must remain unchanged between 2023 and 2024 dataset versions.

Example: Control = Uniform format over time

- ✓ Check 2: All diagnosis codes in 2024 must follow ICD-10; no ICD-9 codes unless change is documented.

Step 3: Calculate the checks

Calculate each check by applying the defined validation rules to the dataset and expressing the result as a quantitative metric. Ensure that calculations are reproducible and clearly linked to the underlying control and business rule.

Step 4: Aggregate scores per criticality

To assess the overall coherence of the dataset, calculate the following three scores:

- Critical coherence score = Average of all critical checks

Critical coherence = (Score of Check 1 + Check 2 + ...) / Number of critical checks

- Non-critical *coherence* score = Average of non-critical checks
non-critical *coherence* = (Score of Check 1 + Check 2 + ...) / Number of non-critical checks

- Total *coherence* score = Average of all check results
Average *coherence* = (Score Check 1 + Score Check 2 +...)/ Total number of checks

Step 5: Report the results in the accuracy template

Document the results of all checks in the reporting template, including scores, applied rules, and criticality classifications to ensure transparency and traceability. Where applicable, include brief commentary on identified issues and potential remediation actions.

5. Validity

5.1. Definition

QUANTUM defines the validity dimension as “the degree to which representations of data in a dataset conform to the specification of a data model or data models”.

This definition ensures that data adheres to the **structural, semantic, and logical constraints** defined by a data model or business specification. This includes compliance with:

- Formats and data types
- Accepted code lists or value domains
- Structural rules (e.g., uniqueness, presence of required fields)
- Derivation logic
- Referential integrity with external systems
- Built-in business or domain constraints

Example 1: Ensuring compliance with HL7 FHIR standards for data exchange.

Example 2: Verifying that ICD-10 codes in a diagnostic column are valid.

Example 3: Validating that data entries conform to predefined care sets (e.g., clinical pathways or specialty-specific documentation templates).

5.2. List of validity controls

Based on the definition in the previous, we distinguish *one* main validity check. To illustrate how this check operates, we use a consistent example throughout: a simplified dataset containing patient records from a fictional healthcare system.

Reference dataset: Patient records

Patient ID	Patient name	Date of birth	Gender	Age	Diagnosis	ICD-10 code	Pregnancy status	Weight (kg)	Height (cm)	BMI	Prescribed medication
100000001	Anna Stevens	03/12/1991	Female	32	Hypertension	I10	Yes	75	170	26	Lisinopril

100000002	Robert White	08/22/1978	Male	45	Prostate cancer	C61	No	82	175	26.8	Atorvastatin
100000003	John Adams	11/04/1989	Male	34	Pregnancy	Z33.1	Yes	70	180	21.6	None
100000004	Lily Martin	06/30/2011	Female	12	Alzheimer's disease	G30	No	60	150	26.7	None
100000005	Grace Brown	12/15/1985	Female	38	Migraine	M123	No	600	220	124	Amlodipine

1. Conformance to data model rules

Definition:

This check evaluates whether data values follow the structural, content, and domain-specific rules defined in a **pre-established data model**. These rules may be:

- **Internally defined** by the organization (e.g., data specifications or business rules);
- **Externally mandated** by regulatory bodies, industry standards (e.g., HL7 FHIR, ICD), or supervisory authorities.

The goal is to ensure data conforms to agreed-upon definitions regarding formats, value domains, data types, structural constraints, and code systems.

Applied to case:

- ✓ Diagnoses should use valid ICD-10 codes.

What to check:

✓ Are ICD-10 codes valid according to the official ICD-10 standard?

Table 2: with valid ICD-10 codes

Patient ID	Patient name	Date of birth	Gender	Age	Diagnosis	ICD-10 code	Pregnancy status	Weight (kg)	Height (cm)	BMI	Prescribed medication
100000001	Anna Stevens	03/12/1991	Female	32	Hypertension	I10	Yes	75	170	26	Lisinopril
100000002	Robert White	08/22/1978	Male	45	Prostate cancer	C61	No	82	175	26.8	Atorvastatin
100000003	John Adams	11/04/1989	Male	34	Pregnancy	Z33.1	Yes	70	180	21.6	None
100000004	Lily Martin	06/30/2011	Female	12	Alzheimer's disease	G30	No	60	150	26.7	None
100000005	Grace Brown	12/15/1985	Female	38	Migraine	M123	No	600	220	124	Amlodipine

Table 2: with valid ICD-10 codes

Diagnosis	ICD-10 code
Hypertension	I10

Prostate cancer	C61
Pregnancy	Z33.1
Alzheimer's Disease	G30

Ways to measure:

What to check	How to calculate	Applied example
% valid coded values	$(\text{Valid records} / \text{Total records}) \times 100$	M123 -> is not a valid ICD-10 code 4 of 5 codes are valid → 80%

5.3. How to apply validity check

1. Critical vs non-critical validity checks

Not all validity violations carry the same risk. To support clearer interpretation and remediation, we distinguish between **critical** and **non-critical** validity checks.

Definition:

- **Critical checks** are considered essential for the dataset to serve its intended purpose. If they fail, the dataset (or relevant part of it) may be considered **unusable** or **unfit for use** until corrected. These typically involve missing values in mandatory fields or key rule violations.

How to apply it:

The criticality classification is applied at the check (or rule) level, not per variable. A single variable can be involved in both critical and non-critical checks depending on the context. Criticality may vary by domain, system, or dataset purpose. While we propose default classifications, organizations are encouraged to define and document criticality based on their specific use cases.

Check type	Typical classification
Conformance to data model rules	● Critical

2. Practical scenarios

This section provides hands-on guidance to help you apply the validity checks outlined in the list of validity controls. It is organized into practical scenarios. *Choose the one scenario that best matches your dataset's context — and follow the corresponding checks.*

Steps:***Step 1: Preparation starts with business rules***

1. Identify business rules that define what “valid” means for the dataset.
 - z. Example: “All diagnosis codes must follow the ICD-10 standard.”
 - aa. Example: “Date of birth must be in the format YYYY-MM-DD.”
 - bb. Example: “Weight must be recorded in kilograms as a numeric value.”.
2. Map each business rule to the relevant consistency control:
 - cc. Conformance to data model rules → Compliance with predefined formats, code lists, structural constraints, and data types.
3. Classify criticality for each rule:
 - dd. Critical: Failure makes the dataset (or part of it) unusable for its intended purpose.
 - ee. Non-critical: Failure reduces quality but does not block use.

Step 2: Define checks from controls

For each control type, define one or more **technical checks** that measure compliance with the associated business rules.

Example: Control = Conformance to data model rules

- ✓ Check 1: All ICD-10 codes must be valid according to the official ICD-10 list.
- ✓ Check 2: Dates must follow the YYYY-MM-DD format.

Step 3: Calculate the checks

Calculate each check by applying the defined validation rules to the dataset and expressing the result as a quantitative metric. Ensure that calculations are reproducible and clearly linked to the underlying control and business rule.

Step 4: Aggregate scores per criticality

To assess the overall validity of the dataset, calculate the following three scores:

- Critical validity score = Average of all critical checks

Critical validity = (Score of Check 1 + Check 2 + ...) / Number of critical checks

- Non-critical *validity* score = Average of non-critical checks
non-critical *validity* = (Score of Check 1 + Check 2 + ...) / Number of non-critical checks

- Total *validity* score = Average of all check results
Average *validity* = (Score Check 1 + Score Check 2 +...)/ Total number of checks

Step 5: Report the results in the validity Template

Document the results of all checks in the reporting template, including scores, applied rules, and criticality classifications to ensure transparency and traceability. Where applicable, include brief commentary on identified issues and potential remediation actions.

6. Precision

6.1. Definition

QUANTUM defines the precision dimension as “*the degree of approximation by which data can represent reality*”.

Precision is the degree of approximation by which data values can represent real-world phenomena, reflecting how closely recorded values mirror the underlying reality and whether they are captured with an appropriate level of resolution and granularity for the dataset’s intended purpose.

- **Resolution** describes the numerical or temporal detail of data values—such as the number of decimal places, significant figures, or timestamp intervals—ensuring small but meaningful variations are preserved and that analyses or decisions can detect critical changes.
- **Granularity** refers to the selection of measurement—such as choosing milligrams over grams for low-dose medications or recording blood pressure as “120/80 mmHg” rather than “normal”—so that data is neither excessively coarse nor misleadingly aggregated.

6.2. List of precision controls

Based on the definition in the previous, we distinguish two main checks that evaluate the precision of a dataset. To illustrate how these checks operate, we use a consistent example throughout: a simplified dataset containing patient records from a fictional healthcare system.

1. Unit-Granularity Alignment control

Definition:

Unit granularity alignment control is the degree to which data provides appropriate unit granularity and numerical detail to meet the requirements of its intended use. This encompasses both selecting measurement units at the correct scale (e.g., milligrams vs. kilograms for pharmaceuticals) and providing sufficient decimal precision within those units to enable accurate calculations, safe decision-making, and proper analysis.

Applied to case:

In the patient dataset, the Dosage column is labelled in gram. Most values fall within the range, but for Lisinopril, Amlodipine with one number after the decimal separator, we can’t say if the unit is precise (dosage might be 0.01-0.09 and have been rounded up).

Table 1: Patient records

Patient ID	Patient name	Date of birth	Sex	Age	Diagnosis	Pregnancy status	Weight (kg)	Height (cm)	BMI	Prescribed medication	Dosage (g)
100000001	Anna Stevens	03/12/1991	Female	32	Hypertension	Yes	75	170	26	Lisinopril	0.1
100000002	Robert White	08/22/1978	Male	45	Prostate cancer	No	82	175	26.8	Atorvastatin	1
100000003	John Adams	11/04/1989	Male	34	Pregnancy	Yes	70	180	21.6	Albuterol	12
100000004	Lily Martin	06/30/2011	Female	12	Alzheimer's disease	No	60	150	26.7	None	0
100000005	Grace Brown	12/15/1985	Female	38	None	No	600	220	124	Amlodipine	0.1

What to check:

- ✓ Are the dosage values recorded with the right level of granularity?

Ways to measure:

What to check	How to calculate	Applied example
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% of records with consistent units	(Number of plausible values within known range / Total records) × 100	3 of 5 values fall within a normal gram range → 60%
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2. Precision check on time interval

Definition:

This check verifies whether timestamps are recorded at the appropriate time granularity (e.g., minute, hour, day) based on the use case.

Applied to case:

If ICU patient monitoring data is recorded only daily instead of every minute or hour, it lacks the temporal resolution needed for timely interventions.

What to check:

- ✓ Are time fields recorded at the required level of temporal detail?

Ways to measure:

What to check	How to calculate	Applied example
% of timestamps meeting interval specification	(Number of values with correct time granularity / Total timestamps) × 100	100 of 120 ICU records have minute-level times → 83.3%

6.3. How to apply precision checks

This section provides hands-on guidance to apply the precision checks from list of precision controls. You first select the scenario that best fits your dataset and then follow the full procedure from preparation to final reporting. Each scenario explains how to prepare your data, which checks to perform, how to aggregate the results into a final precision score, and how to report the outcomes clearly.

1. Critical vs non-critical validity checks

Not all precision requirements have the same impact on usability or reliability of a dataset. We distinguish between **critical** and **non-critical** validity checks.

Definition:

- **Critical checks** are considered essential for the dataset to serve its intended purpose. If they fail, the dataset (or relevant part of it) may be considered **unusable** or **unfit for use** until corrected. These typically involve missing values in mandatory fields or key rule violations.
- **Non-critical checks** are informative but less essential. If they fail, the dataset can still be used, though with reduced reliability or completeness. These checks highlight areas for improvement but do not necessarily block usage.

How to apply it:

The criticality classification is applied at the check (or rule) level, not per variable. A single variable can be involved in both critical and non-critical checks depending on the context. Criticality may vary by domain, system, or dataset purpose. While we propose default classifications, organizations are encouraged to define and document criticality based on their specific use cases.

Check type	Typical classification
Unit consistency	● Critical
Time interval accuracy	● Critical

2. Practical scenarios

This section provides hands-on guidance to help you apply the validity checks outlined in list of precision controls. It is organized into practical scenarios. *Choose the one scenario that best matches your dataset's context — and follow the corresponding checks.*

Steps:

Step 1: Preparation starts with business rules

1. Identify business rules that define what “valid” means for the dataset.
 - ff. Example: “All weights must be recorded in kilograms.”
 - gg. Example: “BMI must be recorded with one decimal place.”
 - hh. Example: “ICU monitoring timestamps must be recorded at minute-level granularity.”
2. Map each business rule to the relevant consistency control:
 - ii. Unit-granularity alignment → All measurements use the same unit.
 - jj. Unit-granularity alignment → All numeric values follow required decimal precision.

kk. Time interval accuracy → All timestamps follow required granularity.

3. Classify criticality for each rule:

II. Critical: Failure makes the dataset (or part of it) unusable for its intended purpose.

mm. Non-critical: Failure reduces quality but does not block use.

Step 2: Define checks from controls

For each control type, define one or more **technical checks** that measure compliance with the associated business rules.

Example: Control = Unit-granularity alignment

Check 1: Weight values fall within a plausible range in kilograms (2–300 kg).

Example: Control = Unit-granularity alignment

Check 2: BMI values recorded with exactly one decimal place.

Example: Control = Time interval accuracy

Check 3: ICU timestamps recorded to the minute.

Step 3: Calculate the checks

Calculate each check by applying the defined validation rules to the dataset and expressing the result as a quantitative metric. Ensure that calculations are reproducible and clearly linked to the underlying control and business rule.

Step 4: Aggregate scores per criticality

To assess the overall precision of the dataset, calculate the following three scores:

- Critical precision score = Average of all critical checks

$\text{Critical precision} = (\text{Score of Check 1} + \text{Check 2} + \dots) / \text{Number of critical checks}$

- Non-critical precision score = Average of non-critical checks

$\text{non-critical precision} = (\text{Score of Check 1} + \text{Check 2} + \dots) / \text{Number of non-critical checks}$

- Total precision score = Average of all check results

$\text{Average precision} = (\text{Score Check 1} + \text{Score Check 2} + \dots) / \text{Total number of checks}$

Step 5: Report the results in the precision Template

Document the results of all checks in the reporting template, including scores, applied rules, and criticality classifications to ensure transparency and traceability. Where applicable, include brief commentary on identified issues and potential remediation actions.

Appendix

Glossary

Term	Definition
Data Quality (DQ)	The degree to which data meets the requirements of completeness, consistency, accuracy, coherence, validity, precision, timeliness, and uniqueness for a specific purpose or use.
QM Label (Quantum Label)	The standardized Data Quality and Utility Label developed in the QUANTUM project to certify and communicate the quality and utility of datasets in the European Health Data Space (EHDS).
Dimension	A specific aspect of data quality assessed by a set of controls and checks. Main dimensions include completeness, consistency, accuracy, coherence, validity, precision, timeliness, and uniqueness.
Control	A general specification or expectation regarding data quality (e.g., "all mandatory fields must be filled"). Controls guide the creation of dataset-specific checks.
Check	A dataset-specific implementation of a control that measures if the dataset meets the expectations (e.g., the percentage of missing values in the field "Date of Birth").
Rule	The business or technical logic that specifies how a control or check operates, often formalized for system execution (e.g., "If Diagnosis = 'Hypertension', field 'Prescribed Medication' must not be empty").

Term	Definition
Completeness	The extent to which all required data are present within a dataset. May be field-level (mandatory fields), conditional (required only in some situations), or cross-dataset (data should be present across multiple linked datasets).
Consistency	The degree to which data values are logically or syntactically the same across or within systems, time, or datasets. Subtypes include cross-field logical, syntactic, cross-system, and longitudinal consistency.
Accuracy	The degree to which data values correctly represent the real-world objects, events, or values they are intended to model. Includes recalculation/performance checks, proxy estimation, deviation analysis, and expert review.
Coherence	The stability and alignment of data definitions, code lists, and structures over time. Coherence checks ensure that business rules, code definitions, or formats stay controlled or are changed only via valid processes.
Validity	The extent to which data values conform to allowed formats, domains, or standards (e.g., diagnosis must have a valid ICD-10 code, blood type must be from a predefined/controlled value list).
Precision	The granularity or level of detail in recorded data and whether it meets the requirements for its intended use (e.g., decimal resolution, category specificity, etc.).

Term	Definition
Duplicate Value	Occurrence of the same value in a field where only unique values are allowed (e.g., unique patient ID).
Criticality	Classification of a check or rule as 'critical', 'mixed', or 'non-critical', indicating its impact on the dataset's fitness for intended use.
Metadata	Data that describe the dataset itself (e.g., provenance, licensing, update frequency), essential for discoverability and interoperability but not directly addressed by core QUANTUM technical checks in this document.
Business Rule	Organizational or domain-specific requirement about data content, format, or relationships (e.g., 'Diagnosis code must be according to ICD-10').

Data Quality Reporting Template (illustrative example)

By following the guidelines, the data holders will be able to report on the Data Quality dimensions. To support the documentation of these reports, HDA will also be providing a Data quality reporting template, highlighting the controls & checks performed for a given dimension.

Dataset Completeness Report

1. General Report Overview

Dataset Name: [Insert Dataset Name]

Date of Analysis: [Insert Date]

Analyst Name: [Insert Name]

Version: [Dataset Version Number]

2. Completeness Analysis (mandatory)

Variable Name	Type of completeness control	Completeness check applied	Nr. of complete records	Nr. of incomplete records	Completeness percentage	Criticality
[Variable 1]	[Mandatory], [Conditional] or [Cross-dataset]	[The check defining expected completeness]	[Count]	[Count]	[Percentage]%	[critical] or [non-critical]
[Variable 2]	[Mandatory], [Conditional] or [Cross-dataset]	[The check defining expected completeness]	[Count]	[Count]	[Percentage]%	[critical] or [non-critical]

Total number of records: [Count]

Critical completeness score: [Percentage]%

Non-critical completeness score: [Percentage]%

Total completeness score: [Percentage]%

3. Breakdown of Missing Data (optional)

This section provides an overview of missing data within the dataset. The level of detail included in the report depends on whether it is for internal or external use.

OPTION 1: External Report

For publicly shared reports, the breakdown of missing data is limited to high-level metadata to maintain privacy and anonymity.

OPTION 2: Internal Report

For internal use, a more detailed breakdown can be provided.